

Title:

Enhancing Data Privacy and Protection in the UK Financial Services Sector Through Cybersecurity

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Abstract

In the dynamic landscape of the UK financial services sector, characterised by extensive digitisation and a pervasive shift towards a cashless society, the preservation of data privacy stands as a paramount challenge. This dissertation addresses the imperative need to enhance data privacy and protection through robust cybersecurity measures. Focusing on the interdependent relationship between data risks, privacy, and security, the research unfolds within the context of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the unique challenges faced by the financial sector. The surge in cyber threats, potential unauthorised access, privacy breaches, and identity theft underscore the critical role of cybersecurity in upholding integrity and trust of financial institutions.

The study embarks on a comprehensive exploration, encompassing a thorough review of data privacy challenges and analysis of cybersecurity gaps. The primary aim is to assess the current state of data privacy within the UK financial services sector and propose effective cybersecurity measures for improvement. The dissertation unfolds as a journey through the complex terrain of data privacy, going through chapters dedicated to the situation analysis, research methodology, findings, developing a framework, a synthesis of the results, a conclusion, and recommendations.

Beyond the financial implications of data breaches, the research delves into the broader societal impact, emphasising the slow erosion of trust from customers and the potential shift to more secure alternatives. As GDPR serves as a catalyst for change, the dissertation provides nuanced insights tailored to the unique challenges faced by the financial services sector. By exploring cybersecurity's role in reinforcing data privacy within GDPR, this study aims to offer actionable solutions, filling critical gaps in existing literature. The dissertation propels the financial sector toward a more secure and privacy conscious future, acknowledging the pivotal role of comprehensive cybersecurity measures in an era where trust in digital transactions is paramount.

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The financial sector serves as a backbone for any economy as it plays a critical role in facilitating financial transactions, managing assets, and safeguarding sensitive customer information. In the UK, there are more than 45 building societies and 300 banks amongst several other financial institutions, making it the most extensive financial system in Europe and the fourth largest globally (Veigas, 2022). Building a strong, stable financial services system that redistributes capital in the economy optimally is the key to economic growth in any country (Bazhenova, et al., 2021). Due to the global rise in cyber threats and the potential for unauthorised access, privacy breaches and identity theft, significant challenges to the integrity and trust of financial institutions are posed. Therefore, cybersecurity emerges as an imperative component in data protection and privacy in the UK financial services sector.

Regulatory compliance has become increasingly important to the financial services industry in recent years. Due to the surge in cloud computing, use of mobile applications and a shift to Internet of Things (IoT), the trend is likely to continue as these factors drive exponential data growth. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is an extension and refinement of existing requirements that were imposed by the 1995 Data Protection Directive. GDPR has been in law since 2018 and it awakened lawyers and the business community because it calls for very high (8 figure) fines and creates internal and external processes to bolster enforcement efforts (Hoofnagle, Van Der Sloot, & Borgesius, 2019). It also enhances the rights of data subjects and gives them more control over what happens to their data. “Financial penalties can be imposed on any organisation that breaches those rights or does not comply with the ‘accountability principle’ – which basically means that data controllers and data processors i.e., organisations and certain individuals – including councils, need to put technical and organisational measures in place to protect the data they hold from loss” (Local Government Association, 2018).

1.2 The Research Problem

The research problem is focused on the need to enhance data privacy in the UK financial services sector, which is crucial for preserving confidentiality and protecting customer information from unauthorised use. The consensus says that companies in the financial sector have taken GDPR in their stride and the reason behind this is that they have a long history of complying with strict data protection and privacy rules set out by financial regulators. Due to this, their strategic approach and detailed procedures are likely to be more mature than those of companies in other sectors. Financial institutions are well aligned to the culture of data risk management and compliance with data protection regulations (Imeson, 2019).

The digital transformation of the financial sector has brought about countless benefits to consumers, businesses and regulators not limited to innovation, competition, and efficiency. However, this transformation also exposes the financial sector to new and evolving risks such as operational disruptions, cyber-attacks, and data breaches. Given the increasing reliance on digital platforms and communication technologies (“ICT”) in the financial sector, these risks can significantly affect financial stability, market integrity, and consumer protection in the UK (Olivi & Venditti, 2023).

In as much as financial institutions have been making a concerted effort to follow provisions set forth by GDPR, it is essential to understand that compliance alone is insufficient to ensure comprehensive data protection and privacy. The Internet and associated information technologies have driven unprecedented innovation, economic value, and access to social services for more than two decades (healey, 2017). Many of these benefits are fuelled by data about individuals that flow through a complex ecosystem. As a result, individuals may not be able to understand the potential consequences for their privacy as they interact with systems, products, and services. Organisations may also not fully realise the consequences due to the complexity of data ecosystems, rapid technological advancements, lack of awareness and expertise, lack of

transparency and user control. Failure to manage privacy risks can have direct adverse consequences at both the individual and societal levels, with follow-on effects on organisations' brands, bottom lines, and prospects for growth. Finding ways to continue to derive benefits from data processing while simultaneously protecting individuals' privacy is challenging, and not well-suited to one-size-fits-all solutions (Boeckl & Lefkowitz, 2020).

Nevertheless, the dynamic and ever-changing realm of cybersecurity threats demands the implementation of supplementary measures to complement GDPR compliance. Cybersecurity includes a broad range of technical and organisational practices that financial institutions must implement to proactively mitigate data privacy risks such as unauthorised access, data breaches and emerging vulnerabilities. Through strengthening their cybersecurity posture and embracing proactive strategies, financial institutions can boost their endeavours to protect data, reinforce confidentiality and nurture trust amongst their customers.

This study is based on the core concepts of data privacy, confidentiality, and cybersecurity within the context of the UK financial services sector. Technological and regulatory data privacy trends are crucial in identifying how best we can safeguard data in an increasingly interconnected world, ensuring that information is securely handled, and individuals' rights are respected. Data Privacy and Innovation are often seen as conflicting goals, where protecting privacy may limit innovation and vice versa. However, privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) offer a solution by allowing the processing of anonymous and encrypted data without sacrificing insights. Anonymization techniques involve transforming sensitive data by removing personal identifiers while preserving the original format. Whereas Pseudonymization aims to identify and modify personally identifiable information (PII) without completely removing it.

Encryption on the other hand typically requires decryption for analysis, which can compromise privacy and result in data expansion. However, homomorphic encryption is an emerging technology that allows third parties to process and manipulate encrypted data without accessing the underlying data in its encrypted form. This technology enables privacy preservation while still allowing data analysis and manipulation (Global Data, 2022).

Regulations, such as GDPR, pose challenges for financial institutions in sharing data for analysis while maintaining customer privacy and data security. Different types of data are subject to specific legal restrictions on usage, making data management and liability concerns more complex (Retail Banker International, 2022). Confidentiality and Cybersecurity is crucial in the financial services sector to protect customer financial data from unauthorised access and cyber threats. Information security, data protection, and cybersecurity theories and frameworks are used to understand the risks and vulnerabilities associated with data disclosure and develop strategies for risk management (Evans, Bond, & Bement, 2003). Legal and regulatory frameworks like GDPR and the Financial Conduct Authority guidelines govern data privacy and cybersecurity in the UK financial services sector.

1.3 Rationale and Justification

In the digital era, the financial services sector relies heavily on the collection, storage, and analysis of vast amounts of customer data. Data risks, Privacy, and security are intertwined and interdependent. However, more than 80% of the financial institutions surveyed by Culp in 2020 treat privacy, data management and information security as separate domains. This approach raises the chances of overlooking crucial responsibilities, resulting in tangible risks and potential costs in terms of both money and reputation for the firms (Culp, 2020).

Everyone seems to be completely reliant on digital payment methods such as debit and credit cards, rendering a cashless society. Therefore, it is crucial to establish adequate cybersecurity measures to ensure the protection of the customer's privacy and data. Financial institutions also face a significant challenge in gaining trust after experiencing data breaches. If a bank's cybersecurity solution is subpar and leads to data breaches, it is highly likely that their customer base will seek services elsewhere.

When a bank's data is compromised, it not only results in loss of time but also money. Recovering from such incidents can be a tedious and unpleasant process, involving tasks like card cancellations, statement reviews, and vigilant monitoring of any issues. The misuse of personal information can have severe consequences. Even if cards are cancelled and fraudulent activities are promptly addressed, sensitive data can still be exploited, potentially exposing the customer to various threats. As a result, financial institutions must exercise greater caution compared to other businesses due to the valuable personal data they possess. Failure to protect their information against cybercrime risks can compromise the bank's integrity and security (Naz, 2023) and may result in litigation costs.

As GDPR promotes heightened data privacy expectations, financial institutions face mounting pressure to enhance their cybersecurity measures and adopt new practices. Consequently, there is a need for greater specificity regarding the definition and criteria for obtaining consent (Eichorn, 2018). Exploring how cybersecurity can reinforce data privacy within GDPR is crucial for compliance and ensuring adherence to regulatory requirements. While Cybersecurity and data privacy have been extensively studied, there is lack of specific research focused on the UK financial services sector system. By investigating the unique challenges and potential solutions within this context we can provide valuable insights and fill existing gaps in the literature, which will be discussed in this research proposal.

1.4 Aim and Objectives

The primary aim of this study is to investigate the challenges and opportunities associated with preserving data confidentiality in the UK financial services sector through the integration of data protection and privacy (Wisniewski, et al., 2022). Specifically, the study seeks to assess the current state of data privacy within the UK financial services sector and explore avenues for improvement by implementing effective cybersecurity measures. The goal is to ensure the utmost confidentiality and protection of sensitive financial information. To achieve this, the study outlines specific objectives, including a comprehensive review of existing cybersecurity frameworks, identification of key data privacy challenges and cybersecurity gaps, a proposal for a tailored cybersecurity framework, and the provision of practical recommendations for financial institutions to strengthen data privacy and protection.

In the ever-evolving landscape of the UK Financial services sector, where the complex intertwine between technology, regulations, and data privacy unfolds, the need to safeguard sensitive customer information has never been more crucial. As the study navigates the complex terrain of data privacy and protection in the financial services sector, formidable challenges come to the forefront. The surge in cyber threats, potential unauthorised access, privacy breaches, and identity theft emphasise the critical role of cybersecurity in upholding the integrity and trust of financial institutions. This research delves into the heart of this dynamic environment, aiming to explore the challenges and opportunities in maintaining data confidentiality. The journey unfolds through a comprehensive exploration of the current risk landscape, the existing cybersecurity controls and horizon scanning to produce a proposal for a robust cybersecurity framework ensuring the confidentiality and protection of sensitive financial information. In the chapters that follow, a detailed expedition through the literature review, research methodology, findings of the study, the end deliverable process, the synthesis of the results, and finally, the conclusion and recommendations, each attributes a vital piece to this dissertation.

1.5 Impact Statement

Amidst the pervasive digitisation of financial services and the relentless rise of a cashless society, the dissertation assumes pivotal significance. By scrutinising the symbiotic relationship between data risks, privacy, and security, the research seeks to disrupt prevalent notions that treat these domains as discrete entities. In a landscape where trust in digital transactions is paramount, the dissertation emphasises the critical need for comprehensive cybersecurity measures. As financial institutions grapple with the aftermath of data breaches, the study highlights the potential ramifications, not just in terms of financial losses but also the slow loss of trust from customers and the risk that they may switch to safer options. Beyond financial implications, the dissertation acknowledges that the broader societal impact emphasises the need for institutions to exercise heightened caution in protecting valuable personal data. With GDPR serving as a catalyst for change offering nuanced insights tailored to the unique challenges faced by the UK financial services sector. Through its exploration of cybersecurity's role in reinforcing data privacy within GDPR, the dissertation aims to provide actionable solutions, filling critical gaps in existing literature and propelling the financial sector toward a more secure and privacy-conscious future.

Chapter 2 Situational Analysis

This chapter stands as a pivotal segment of this dissertation, making the junction of thorough literature review and critical examination. This chapter will delve into the complex risk landscape surrounding data privacy and protection, dissecting the myriad of challenges that currently permeate the UK financial services sector. It will scrutinise the existing cybersecurity controls and policies, evaluating their effectiveness and identifying prevailing gaps. Furthermore, the chapter will engage in horizon scanning, anticipating future trends and potential threats that could shape the path of cybersecurity. By weaving together theoretical insights and practical findings, this analysis will lay a robust foundation for the subsequent development of a proactive framework aimed at enhancing data privacy and safeguarding against cyber threats.

2.1 Risk landscape

2.1.1 Escalating Threats and Challenges: Data Privacy Dynamics in the UK Financial Services Sector

The incidence of cybersecurity breaches in UK financial services firms has tripled between periods 2021-2022 and 2022-2023, with the pensions sector reporting the highest number of breaches. A report by the international law firm Reynolds Porter Chamberlain (RPC), reported 246 breaches. Achi Lewis, the area VP for EMEA at Absolute Software, commented on this trend, stating, 'for many sectors, the question is no longer 'if' but 'when' an attack will occur'. Given the financial sector's critical role in our global economy, handling extensive sensitive data and financial transactions daily, it becomes a prime target for malicious actors. Consequently, the urgency of cyber resilience has never been more crucial. This entails not only implementing robust preventive measures but also establishing a proactive response mechanism capable of adapting swiftly and recovering in the face of an attack (Mcquaid, 2023).

Sharing personally identifiable information (PII) during business transactions has become

a routine occurrence for most individuals, encompassing the disclosure of financial details like bank and loan account numbers, credit/debit card information, as well as non-financial PII such as names, social security numbers, driver's licence details, addresses, and email addresses. In essence, there is an overwhelming volume of personally identifiable information that the financial, capital markets, and insurance industries handle as an integral part of their day-to-day operations.

Considering the escalating threat of data breaches, identity theft, and associated fraudulent activities across various sectors, companies are placing increasing emphasis on enhancing their data privacy programs. While the concern of data breaches extends to all industries, the financial services sector stands out as a primary target for fraudsters due to the inherent value of the data it holds. This section delves into the significance of data privacy specifically from the perspective of the financial services industry, emphasising the challenges that firms encounter in their daily business operations.

Financial services institutions demand more rigorous data security standards compared to other industries due to their unique operational structure. These firms routinely handle substantial volumes of personal and confidential customer information, encompassing details like bank account information, debit or credit card data, and other sensitive business-related customer data. The existence of data privacy regulations and the potential reputational risks stemming from breach events amplify the importance of implementing robust data privacy policies. The success or failure of a financial service firm hinges on its ability to navigate the delicate balance between utilising confidential customer information for operational purposes and preserving privacy. To seize emerging growth opportunities, financial firms must exhibit flexibility in sharing confidential customer data across various departments, affiliated partners, or non-affiliated third parties, such as technology or outsourcing firms – all while adhering to regulations and safeguarding the company's reputation. The crux lies in striking this delicate equilibrium between data sharing flexibility and maintaining vigorous data privacy measures (Blake, et al., 2018).

Ensuring data privacy remains a primary concern for both companies and governments

globally. Most countries have implemented privacy laws and regulations aimed at safeguarding personal and sensitive customer data from misuse. These laws establish guidelines for companies regarding the utilisation, storage, and processing of such data. For instance, the U.S. has enacted regulations requiring companies to promptly notify clients of data breaches when they occur. Data privacy laws are prevalent in nearly all major countries worldwide, covering aspects such as data security, accountability, access, integrity, consent, disclosure, and notice. However, the strictness of these laws and their enforcement varies. The subsequent presentation categorises major countries based on the degree of stringency in their privacy regulations and enforcement. Germany and Argentina boast the most restrictive laws, explicitly prohibiting data transfers to countries lacking adequate data protection regulations. Most of the other Western European Countries fall within the restrictive category.

Amidst growing scrutiny from regulators and the media, financial services institutions confront mounting pressure to uphold stringent data security standards. In the present landscape, financial firms encounter distinct challenges while addressing privacy concerns and adhering to regulations.

- **Information Flexibility:** Financial Service Institutions must facilitate dynamic access to sensitive customer data for clients, employees, and external partners. This constant exchange of information poses difficulties in safeguarding data.
- **Proliferation of social media:** The extensive use of social networking sites for brand building and customer relationship management presents a dual challenge. While social media offers a cost-effective marketing avenue and improved customer connections. It introduces complexities in maintaining data security.
- **Sophisticated External Hackers:** Cybercriminals employ advanced viruses, malware, and tactics to outsmart traditional data security technologies, posing an escalating threat to financial firms.
- **Employee Education in Data Protection:** Despite the presence of automated Data Loss Prevention (DLP) solutions, employees remain pivotal in preventing data leaks and handling sensitive information. Consistently educating both new and

existing staff about diverse security issues presents an ongoing challenge (Ejanthkar, Vaidyanath, & Sullivan, 2012).

In the realm of commercial banking, both data privacy and cybersecurity present risks that extend to an institution's clients and the overall stability and integrity of the institution itself. Considering this, regulatory bodies in the UK, such as the Prudential Regulation Authority (PRA) and the Bank of England (BoE), are keen on advancing metrics, controls, and standards to fortify information protection. The PRA has consistently emphasised the menace of cyber threats to financial institutions, categorising them as the primary risk confronting financial institutions today. Additionally, the BoE emphasises the critical role of information security in fulfilling its mandate of upholding stability and public confidence in the UK's financial system (Nazarro, White, & Setterlund, 2017).

2.1.2 Challenges Faced by UK Financial Institutions in Cybersecurity

This topic delves into the intricate web of challenges faced by Financial Institutions, exploring the dynamic nature of cyber threats and the critical measures required to enhance data protection in the sector. The research aims to highlight the diverse array of cyber threats faced by the UK, extending beyond Eastern European geopolitics. These threats are attracted by the nation's economic significance. Specifically, the study delves into the vulnerabilities of the UK Financial services sector, which has increasingly transitioned to online platforms, making it susceptible to cyber-attacks. Given that this sector typically stores substantial volumes of customer data, the state of its cybersecurity is of paramount importance.

The report written by threat analyst (Koldobsky, 2022) suggests that various types of leaked data provide cyber attackers with the means to execute multifaceted attacks on companies. This could involve tactics like social engineering or directly infiltrating a company's systems using the exposed information discovered online. The compromised

data often encompasses sensitive details like source codes, personal information, contact details, login credentials or various services (including internal systems typically restricted to company personnel), and more. The demand for UK-specific data among cybercriminals is evident, as demonstrated by a post on a Russian speaking cybercrime forum requesting “UK database leaks” on January 19, 2021.

Figure 1- Screenshot of the User ‘newagechop’ requesting for database leaks from the UK (Koldobsky, 2022)

Frequent occurrences of such messages can be observed on dark web forums. Similar offers surface either as responses or as independent posts. For instance, user JbL” on the now defunct English-speaking cybercrime forum Raid Forums posted an offer to sell a database containing names, phone numbers, dates of birth, and additional information of individuals based in the UK.

Figure 2- Screenshot of Offer to Sell Database with individuals' information (Koldobsky, 2022).

In the screenshot below a user on a dark web forum is seen to be requesting specific details for UK targeted bank leads.

Figure 3 - Screenshot of discussion on dark web forum of a user requesting specific targeted bank leads (Koldobsky, 2022).

The research from the KELA report by (Koldobsky, 2022) suggests that between January 17,2021, and February 17, 2022, nearly 17,000 credentials linked to prominent financial institutions in the UK were disclosed. Among these credentials, over 1,000 email

addresses were duplicated, indicating approximately 16,000 unique values. Most of the disclosed credentials (66%) lacked passwords, while 33% had diverse password types, including BCRYPT (17% of passwords), SHA1(7%), MD5 (5%), and Plaintext (3%), as depicted in the graph depicted in [figure 4](#).

Figure 4 - Screenshot of the number of credentials leaked per password type.

As seen in the graph above, most of the leaked credentials did not have a password.

Following Russia’s premeditated attack on Ukraine, the National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) has been calling on organisations in the UK to bolster their online defences. (NCSC, 2022). UK organisations are therefore strongly encouraged to follow the actionable steps in the NCSC guidance that reduce the risk of falling victim to an attack.

2.1.3 Dynamics of the Global Cybersecurity landscape in the financial services sector

In recent times, the financial sector emerged as the second most targeted industry concerning reported data breaches. On a global scale, finance and insurance organisations collectively faced 566 breaches by December 2022, leading to the exposure of over 254 million records. Ransomware attacks targeting financial services have exhibited a substantial increase, climbing from 55% in 2022 to 64% in 2023, almost doubling the 34% reported in 2021. Of significant concern is the fact that merely 1 in 10 attacks were intercepted before encryption occurred, resulting in a striking 81% of organisations succumbing to data encryption.

The financial sector bore the second-highest costs related to data breaches across all industries, reaching a total of £4.9 million. These trends and challenges emphasise the global nature of cybersecurity threats, raising concerns about their potential impact on the UK's financial institutions and the imperative for enhanced protective measures.

In the contemporary landscape, cybersecurity stands out as a major concern for banks, primarily due to the increasing digitisation of clients, exposing them to heightened risks of hacking. Extensive files containing sensitive information, including company procedures, customer records, and confidential data, face the threat of deletion without proper safeguards. A cybersecurity breach poses significant repercussions for both personal and commercial consumers, leading to potential credibility damage. The demand for IoT devices is rapidly rising in the Banking, Financial Services, and Insurance (BFSI) sector, commonly referred to as smart gadgets in everyday life. However, cybercriminals, recognising monetary opportunities, escalate and diversify their attacks. Consumers who embrace Internet of Things (IoT) gadgets face the risk of unforeseen threats, where seemingly safe methods can transform into authoritative tools for criminal activities. These threats encompass malicious crypto money withdrawal, DDoS assaults, or botnet activities that demand the disclosure of computer information. When malware infiltrates the victim's IoT system, it gains control of the individual's PC and executes

harmful operations (Arul & Punidha, 2022).

Insights from the 2022 Cybersecurity and Financial System Resilience Report (Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System, 2022), identified concerns on cybersecurity specifically emphasising prominent risks posed by Ransomware-as-a-Service and highly sophisticated Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks to the operational continuity and customer data protection of financial institutions.

Ransomware-as-a-Service (Raas) is distinguished by its elevated sophistication, rapid proliferation, and the inherent challenge of attribution. This model enables threat actors to create templates akin to “franchised” threats. Accomplished threat actors license their software to other malicious entities, often in exchange for a share of the ransom proceeds. This approach extends the reach of less advanced threat actors, providing them with numerous avenues to disrupt businesses. Entities declining ransom payment frequently face the daunting task of reconstructing their infrastructure to restore normal business operations (Sentinel One, 2023).

Sophisticated Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, on the other hand, aim to incapacitate a machine or network resource by inundating the target or its surrounding infrastructure with an overwhelming volume of traffic. The financial services sector has long been a prime target for DDoS attacks, impacting not only the targeted institutions but also extending to associated external entities and stakeholders (Sentinel One, 2023).

As of the current period, numerous financial services organisations are actively engaged in the restoration of their networks following disruptive cyber-attacks. Banks and financial technology firms worldwide have reported incidents of ransom and extortion attempts,

highlighting the pervasive threat from cyber criminals. Additionally, disruptions such as the suspension of overnight automatic teller machine (ATM) transactions and distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks impacting stock exchange-related websites further emphasise the challenges posed by cyber threats in the financial sector. The repercussions of such disruptions extend beyond immediate customer impact, casting a shadow on the confidence of fellow financial services entities. Recognising the escalating threat of cyber-attacks, regulatory bodies globally are intensifying their scrutiny, catapulting operational resilience to the forefront of agendas worldwide.

A few years ago, the occurrence of targeted attacks on financial services sector firms was relatively uncommon. However, in recent years, the frequency of such cases has surged, propelled by advancements in capabilities and specialised techniques like network intrusion. In collaboration with Carnegie Endowment for International Peace (CEIP), BAE Systems has meticulously documented public instances through the Timeline of Cyber Incidents Involving Financial Institutions (CEIP, 2022). This timeline proves to be a valuable tool for monitoring trends, recognising that publicly disclosed cases represent only a fraction of the actual volume of incidents and near misses (Nish, Naumaan, & Muir, 2020).

In 2023, the banking sector has witnessed a notable surge in ransomware attacks, primarily driven by the widespread adoption of Ransomware-as-a-Service (Raas) and Hacking-as-a-Service (Haas). The State of Ransomware Report 2023 by Sophos (Sophos, 2023), indicates a significant increase in ransomware attacks in financial services, rising from 55% in 2022 to 64% in the 2023 study, nearly doubling the 34% reported in 2021. Phishing emerges as the most prevalent method for initial access, emphasising the need for banks to address this primary entry point.

1. Increased Risks in Supply Chain

Supply chain cyberattacks are on the rise in terms of both frequency and sophistication. Financial Institutions, relying heavily on privileged access to third party software, are particularly vulnerable to supply chain vulnerabilities. Malicious actors exploit communication channels between vendor networks and end-user devices, making safeguarding this critical juncture imperative.

2. Rapid Surge in ATO (Account Takeover) Attacks

The digital shift accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic has expanded the pool of potential fraud targets within the digital financial ecosystem. Financial services face a significant threat from Account Takeover (ATO) attacks, with 37.8% experiencing an attack in 2022. Sift's Digital Trust & Safety Index reports a startling 131% increase in ATO attacks in the first half of 2022 alone. This trend necessitates heightened vigilance and proactive defence mechanisms.

3. Rise of DDoS Attacks Fuelled by Geopolitical Conflicts

The conflict between Russia and Ukraine has led to a substantial increase in Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks targeting financial institutions. In 2022, European financial firms witnessed a 73% surge in DDoS attacks, as reported by FS-ISAC and Akamai (FS-ISAC, AKAMAI, 2023). The global rise of 22% compared to the previous year emphasises the urgent need to counteract these attacks, capable of disrupting services and eroding customer trust.

In today's business landscape, technology and data have become integral to nearly every facet of operations, spanning from customer information and intellectual property to HR records. This digital transformation is not confined to technology or IT enterprises alone; rather, workplaces overall are evolving into digital environments. The extensive dependence on technology brings with it significant cybersecurity risks. Organisations that underestimate the importance of cybersecurity and fall victim to successful cyberattacks face substantial financial and reputational consequences. (Grant Thornton,

2015) carried out an assessment that suggests that in 2015, the worldwide cost of cyber-attacks was consecutively estimated to be at least \$315 billion (est. GBP247 billion), emphasising the gravity of the situation.

Internationally, the financial sector faces significant cyber risk, regardless of whether it operates in a low-income or developed economy. The International Telecommunication Union of the United Nations has introduced the Global Cyber Security Index to enhance the monitoring of this risk. Notably, the scrutiny of cyber security is most pronounced in Europe, America, and Asia, as illustrated in [figure 5](#) below which depicts the Global Cybersecurity Index for the year 2017 (Boitan, 2020).

Figure 5 - The Global Cyber Security Index (Bouveret, 2018).

While the outlook appears positive, there is a shared belief among cybersecurity experts that achieving absolute cybersecurity for an IT system is a challenging task, given the diverse array of external and internal threats. Cyber risk, like other forms of fraud risks, can be lessened but is unlikely to be entirely eradicated (CEPS, 2018).

Cyber incidents categorised as data breaches encompass the theft of customer data or funds from customer accounts, unauthorised access to customer information and databases through internal logins, phishing, and disruptions to business operations. Fraud carried out via internet banking, mobile banking, or phone banking fall under the classification of remote banking fraud losses, sharing a common element: a fraudster gains access to an individual’s bank account and conducts an unauthorised money transfer from that account (Boitan, 2020).

The study conducted by the European Confederation of Institutes of Internal Auditing (ECIIA, 2020), involving heads of internal audit departments in nine European Countries, unveiled a list of key topics they have been monitoring in recent years along with prospects. The findings are noteworthy, indicating that cyber security and data protection are prominent concerns as depicted in [figure 6](#).

2018	2019	2020
1. GDPR and the data protection challenge	1. Cybersecurity: IT governance & third parties	1. Cybersecurity & data privacy: rising expectations of internal audit
2. Cybersecurity: a path to maturity	2. Data protection & strategies in a post-GDPR world	2. The increasing regulatory burden
3. Regulatory complexity and uncertainty	3. Digitalisation, automation & AI: technology adoption risks	3. Digitalisation & business model disruption
4. Pace of innovation	4. Sustainability: the environment & social ethics	4. Looking beyond third parties
5. Political uncertainty: Brexit and other unknowns	5. Anti-bribery & anti-corruption compliance	5. Business resilience, brand value & reputation
6. Vendor risk and third party assurance	6. Communication risk: protecting brand & reputation	6. Financial risks: from low returns to rising debt
7. The culture conundrum	7. Workplace culture: discrimination & staff inequality	7. Geopolitical instability & the macroeconomy
8. Workforces: planning for the future	8. A new era of trade: protectionism & sanctions	8. Human capital: the organisation of the future
9. Evolving the internal audit function	9. Risk governance & controls: adapting to change	9. Governance, ethics & culture: the exemplary organisation
	10. Auditing the right risks: taking a genuinely risk-based approach	10. Climate change: risk vs opportunity

Figure 6 - Exploring Focus areas analysed by Internal Audit Departments (ECIIA, 2020).

Figure 7 - The top risks that your organisation currently faces. 2021 (orange) 2022 (blue) (ECIIA, 2022) .

2.1.4 Insider Threats in Financial Institutions

Financial Institutions have faced heightened risks involving personnel and contractors since 2020, stemming from the adoption of remote access to core banking services and operational support systems. This shift also involved granting expanded access permissions to facilitate remote work. Despite Implementing controls like MFA (Multi-factor Authentication) to counter unauthorised buy insiders, their effectiveness has not been consistent, particularly when misconfigured or when system vulnerabilities are identified. Addressing challenges posed by insider threats remains an ongoing priority for financial institutions, necessitating continuous monitoring and remediation efforts (Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System, 2022). Given the evolving landscape of insider threats, it's crucial to recognise that former and current employees, contractors, and other organisational "insiders" pose a substantial threat. This is primarily due to their in-depth knowledge of and access to their employers' systems and/or databases, coupled with their ability to bypass existing physical and electronic security measures through legitimate means.

2.1.5 Managing Risks in Cybersecurity

The Chartered Institute of Internal Auditors (EIIA, 2018) emphasises the importance of fostering a robust cyber awareness culture as a key defence against cyber-attacks. It emphasises that the internal audit function plays a critical role in ensuring the understanding and effective implementation of this culture across all levels of staff. The establishment of a comprehensive cyber risk management framework involves defining multiple layers of risk defence, including those represented by the financial institution's board, executive management function, and the three lines of defence-comprising operational management, risk/internal control/compliance departments, and internal audit.

(UK Finance, 2019) emphasises the need for the financial industry to enhance its commitment in combatting fraud and scams through various measures. These include the implementation of advanced security systems for customer protection, incorporating real-time transaction analysis, sophisticated authentication methods for customers, and the utilisation of behavioural biometrics on devices and technology. Additionally, they propose the creation of a banking protocol designed to function as a rapid warning and response scheme, enabling bank branch staff to alert the police in cases of suspected fraud. Furthermore, the development of new technology aims to track suspicious payments and identify accounts associated with money mule activities.

The Centre for European Policy Studies (CEPS, 2018) has taken a complementary initiative by organising a Task Force meeting, gathering experts from the financial industry, tech sector, national supervisors, and European Institutions. The resulting policy recommendations aim to enhance the financial industry's cyber resilience against present and future threats. These recommendations include the need for increased convergence in defining cyber-incidents, deciding on data sharing with supervisors and customers, development of reliable cyber-trend statistics, implementation of best practices for cyber

hygiene by regulators and supervisors, strengthening the European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme, reinforcing cross-border cooperation and legal convergence within the EU and globally, designing best practices for resolving cyber-attack cases, and assessing the feasibility and necessity of creating an emergency fund for large-scale cyber-attacks.

The analysis carried out by (Siddiqi, 2020) emphasises that cyber-risk remains a persistent challenge. The financial industry's prompt development and implementation of a harmonised framework, along with heightened risk awareness and management, can enhance resilience against ongoing risk. (Siddiqi, 2020) also estimates that cybercrime could incur global costs of around \$350 billion (est. GBP247 billion) for banks in the next five years, therefore emphasising the urgency of taking rapid actions, noting that larger financial institutions tend to report risk mitigations as work in progress.

2.1.6 Implications for the Financial Services Sector

In response to the ever-evolving cyber threat landscape, financial institutions must adopt a vigilant and proactive approach to fortify their cybersecurity posture. The integration of technology expands potential vulnerabilities, demanding a comprehensive response. By adhering to key regulatory requirements, financial institutions can enhance their resilience and security posture, mitigating risks effectively (Hagelauer & Sarkar, 2023).

Figure 8-Rate of Ransomware Attacks by country: 2022 vs. 2023 (Sophos, 2023).

Figure 9- Rate of Ransomware Attacks by Industry (Sophos, 2023).

The graphs represented [figure 8](#) and [figure 9](#) provide valuable insights into the evolving landscape of ransomware attacks, highlighting both country specific and industry-wide trends. In 2022, the United Kingdom experienced a significant ransomware attack of 57%, reflecting the prevalence of cyber threats in the region. However, the data for 2023 reveals a noteworthy decline to 44%, suggesting potential improvements in cybersecurity

measures or shifts in threat dynamics.

In parallel, the industry-specific breakdown underscores the financial sector's heightened vulnerability, with a ransomware attack rate of 64%. This emphasises the critical need for robust cybersecurity strategies within financial institutions to address the evolving tactics employed by threat actors. The disparity between country specific and industry-specific rates highlights the nuanced nature of cyber threats, necessitating tailored approaches to mitigate risks effectively. These findings underscore the urgency for ongoing vigilance, proactive defence mechanisms, and strategic investments in cybersecurity infrastructure to safeguard both national and sectoral interests.

The evolution of banking technology within the landscape of digital transformation has ushered in numerous opportunities such as innovative financial products like cryptocurrencies, digital investment platforms and Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL) Services for banks and large financial institutions. However, accompanying these advancements come with distinctive challenges. The convergence of hybrid work dynamics, intensified competition from fintech entities, and evolving customer expectations has compelled banks to rapidly adapt their technology operating models and enhance customer offerings. This swift transformation introduces novel risks, encompassing cyber security, data privacy, business disruption, and the potential infringement of intellectual property (IP).

The imperative for risk mitigation within the financial services sector has reached unprecedented levels. As banks undergo a transformation, positioning themselves as technology entities, regulatory bodies in banking are closely scrutinising the adaptability of risk management frameworks to the rapid pace of change. Simultaneously, financial institutions grappled with substantial financial ramifications, paying out approximately £1 Billion in ransomware cases throughout 2021. Gary Kausmeyer, Executive Vice President, and Chief Risk Officer at Capital Bank emphasised the escalating discussions within risk and security spheres. Kausmeyer advocates for a heightened focus on cybersecurity infrastructure investments, stressing that these measures are no longer

mere 'nice-to-haves.'

Expanding through acquisitions introduces an additional layer of complexity to cybersecurity challenges. In the words of Zahira (Zah) Rodriguez Gonzalvo, Senior Vice President, and Head of Financial, Climate, and Operational Risk, at Banco Popular, acquiring systems and assets inherently means acquiring associated risks. This broadens the spectrum of technological and digital risks that institutions need to effectively manage. While the cloud serves as a resilient network during cyber-attacks, financial firms encounter new risks within this environment, particularly related to data privacy and security. The sensitivity of customer data adds an extra layer of concern (AON, 2022).

The quantity of significant cyber incidents reported to the FCA within a given calendar year serves as a reliable indicator of the resilience demonstrated by financial sector firms. In 2016, the FCA revealed the reception of 90 reports of material cyber incidents, a figure that climbed to 106 in 2019 before receding to 76 in 2020. Notably FOI data for 2021 highlights a 52% increase, with the number reaching 116 (PICUS, 2021).

Figure 10 -Number of material cyber incidents reported to the FCA between 2019 and 2021 (PICUS, 2021).

Over 25% of the reported material, cyber incidents to the FCA in 2021 were attributed to ransomware, reflecting a 20% surge compared to 2020 in total. This emphasises the pervasive threat of ransomware to UK businesses. Major players in ransomware, including Lazarus, Cobalt, and Fin7, exhibited heightened activity in 2021, especially targeting financial institutions. The uptick in ransomware related incidents in 2021 is a significant concern especially considering that the average cost of a ransomware attack for UK finance firms has reached £1.4 million.

Figure 11 - Total number of ransomware incidents reported to the FCA (PICUS, 2021).

On March 7, 2021, the European Banking Authority (EBA) disclosed a cyber-attack on its Microsoft Exchange Servers. Researchers from Picus Labs suggest these attack campaigns may have impacted numerous other organisations within the finance sector (PICUS, 2021).

2.1.7 Cyber Incidents Involving Financial Institutions

2.1.7.1 NFT Investments

NFT Investments, a British firm specialising in investing in companies developing fungible tokens, reported a cyber-attack resulting in the loss of \$250,000 (est. GBP197,000) in assets in January 2023. The company identified a fraudulent phishing attack from an

unknown external source, prompting the immediate implementation of its incident response plan. Additionally, the company plans to commission a third-party report to investigate the incident's circumstances, although details of how the assets were lost were not disclosed (Martin, 2023).

The following breach incidents were derived from the (Carnegie Endowment For International Peace, 2023) timeline for cyber incidents.

UK and Italian banks targeted by SharkBot banking trojan

NOVEMBER 1

In late October 2021, researchers from Cleafy and ThreatFabric discovered a new Android banking Trojan called SharkBot.

CLOSE ▾

TARGET
Location: Italy, United Kingdom Date Breach First Reported: 11/1/2021

INCIDENT
Method: Malware
Type: Multiple

ACTOR
Type: Unknown
Attribution: Unknown

DESCRIPTION
In late October 2021, researchers from Cleafy and ThreatFabric discovered a new Android banking Trojan called SharkBot. The trojan tricks targets into downloading malicious apps from Google Play Store and grants itself admin rights, collects keystrokes, intercepts/hides F2A SMS messages, and accesses mobile banking and cryptocurrency apps to transfer funds. SharkBot has been detected targeting international banks from the United Kingdom and Italy and five different cryptocurrency services.

Figure 12 - UK and Italian banks targeted by Sharkbot banking trojan (Carnegie Endowment For International Peace, 2023)

UK Insurer Recovers from Ransomware Attack

MAY 25

On May 25, 2021, UK-based insurance firm One Call stated that it had successfully restored its systems onto a new environment separate from the one that was impacted by a ransomware attack on May 13, adding that a ransomware note purportedly from DarkSide could not be verified as authentic.

CLOSE ▾

TARGET

Location: United Kingdom
Date Breach First Reported: 5/25/2021

INCIDENT

Method: Ransomware
Type: Theft

ACTOR

Type: Unknown
Attribution: Unknown

DESCRIPTION

On May 25, 2021, UK-based insurance firm One Call stated that it had successfully restored its systems onto a new environment separate from the one that was impacted by a ransomware attack on May 13, adding that a ransomware note purportedly from DarkSide could not be verified as authentic.

Figure 13 - UK Insurer Recovers from Ransomware Attack (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2023).

Metro Bank 2FA Breach

FEBRUARY 2

UK-based Metro Bank became the first major bank to suffer from a new type of cyber intrusion that intercepts text messages with two-factor authentication codes used to verify various customer transactions.

CLOSE ▾

TARGET

Location: United Kingdom
Date Breach First Reported: 2/2/2019

INCIDENT

Method: Other
Type: Disruption

ACTOR

Type: Unknown
Attribution: Unknown

DESCRIPTION

UK-based Metro Bank became the first major bank to suffer from a new type of cyber intrusion that intercepts text messages with two-factor authentication codes used to verify various customer transactions. The attackers exploited flaws in the Signaling System 7 (SS7) protocol, which is used by telecommunications companies to route text messages around the world. A spokesperson for the bank stated that only a small number of those defrauded were Metro Bank customers.

Figure 14 - Metro Bank 2FA Breach (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2023).

Magecart Payments Breach

NOVEMBER 2

In early November, Lloyds Banking Group and other UK banks were forced to replace payment cards after the breach of numerous retail sites.

[CLOSE](#) ▾

TARGET

Location: United Kingdom
Date Breach First Reported: 11/2/2018

INCIDENT

Method: Other
Type: Theft

ACTOR

Type: Unknown
Attribution: Unknown

DESCRIPTION

In early November, Lloyds Banking Group and other UK banks were forced to replace payment cards after the breach of numerous retail sites. Websites for retailers, including Ticketmaster and British Airways, were manipulated to skim card information from hundreds of thousands of customers using the Magecart toolset.

Figure 15 - Magecart Payments Breach (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2023).

2.2 Current Cybersecurity Measures and Protocols in the Financial Services Sector.

2.2.2 Strategic Approaches and Initiatives in Financial Cybersecurity

Cybersecurity constitutes a strategic process aimed at safeguarding computers, servers, networks, and digital data from unauthorised access, destruction, or cyber-attacks. Within the financial services sector, organisations prioritise the protection of their financial data, intellectual properties, and overall reputation as integral components of their business strategy. The objectives extend beyond safeguarding confidential information, emphasising the need to ensure information availability and maintain its integrity. Given that information security is a critical aspect of data privacy and protection, numerous organisations are developing comprehensive strategies to secure information in the cyberspace. Recognising the security challenges posed by technological advancements, institutions focus on employing both technical and legal measures to resist the illegal use of information. A study by the UK Government's Cyber Security Centre (National Cyber Security Centre, 2017) revealed that nearly 50% of UK companies experienced cyber breaches or attacks in the preceding year. Despite this, the UK Government has pledged a \$2.5 billion (est. GBP1.97 billion) investment to fortify the country against cyber-attacks, aiming to establish the UK as a secure environment for living and conducting online business. In response, institutions within the financial services sector must take proactive measures to secure digital consumer data. This includes implementing awareness programs, providing e-Training, offering foundational cyber courses, and offering free consultations (Alawi & Bassam, 2020).

2.2.3 Key Regulatory Considerations for Financial Institutions

In Europe, efforts to enhance cybersecurity involve collaboration between the European Commission, other European authorities, central banks, and industry professionals. In 2013, the European Commission implemented a Cyber Security Strategy for the European Union, followed by the adoption of the Network and Information Security Directive 2016. The directive aimed to reinforce European cyber security regulations by introducing new requirements for information security and incident notification for operators of essential services and digital service providers. Additionally, the year 2016 saw the enforcement of the General Data Protection Regulation, representing a significant transformation in European data protection laws. Another influential international entity contributing to the global financial integrity landscape is the International Monetary Fund (Boitan, 2020).

The strategy on Anti-Money Laundering and Combating the Financing of Terrorism, initially introduced in 2014, has recently undergone revision and updates as per the 2019 report from the International Monetary Fund (International Monetary Fund, 2019). This revision aims to delineate the Fund's continued involvement in various domains that have the potential to adversely impact financial integrity, including areas such as Fintech, illicit financial flows, and pertinent aspects of cyber security. The chartered Institute of Internal Auditors (Chartered Institute of Internal Auditors, 2023) cautions that upcoming regulations will heighten the demands on organisations to establish robust cybersecurity strategies and foster a cybersecurity culture. This entails the implementation of stringent controls and policies to thwart and address cyber-attacks effectively.

2.2.4 Tools for quantifying Exposure to Cyber Risk

To enhance regulatory frameworks, it is essential to incorporate suitable tools for quantifying exposure to cyber risk. In this context, the International Monetary Fund (Bouveret, 2018), has devised a quantitative framework for evaluating cyber risk within the financial sector. Similarly, the Bank of England has introduced the CBEST framework, which facilitates controlled and intelligence-led cyber security tests for systematic financial Institutions in the UK. This framework is designed to identify potential network entry points from the target organisation's website, pinpoint vulnerabilities exploitable by malicious actors, and simulate a cyber-attack using the tactics, techniques, and procedures of threat actors known to be interested in the target organisation.

2.2.5 Compliance and Key Regulations

Amid the dynamic threat landscape, financial institutions must uphold vigilance and regularly assess the effectiveness of their regulatory and oversight systems. Compliance with the following regulations is crucial to prevent penalties and preserve the integrity of the financial ecosystem.

1. FCA Operational Resilience Guidelines: The FCA's PS21/3 operational resilience guidelines outline obligations for financial services firms to establish robust measures for managing severe operational disruptions, including cyberattacks. Financial Institutions are mandated to identify critical business services, establish impact tolerances, and conduct thorough mapping and testing, addressing vulnerabilities related to cybersecurity.
2. PSD2 SCA: The introduction of Strong Customer Authentication (SCA) to PSD2 mandates financial institutions and payment service providers to implement multi-factor authentication for online payments beyond a specified threshold, enhancing security and mitigating fraudulent transactions.
3. UK-GDPR and Data Protection Act 2018: GDPR and the Data Protection Act 2018

impose stringent requirements on banks, emphasising the protection of personal data, consent, data breach notifications, and the appointment of data protection officers. Compliance not only avoids fines but also reinforces customer trust through responsible handling of sensitive information.

2.2.6 GDPR Compliance Challenges and Solutions

The financial Services industry, which heavily relies on data for decision making, fraud detection, compliance, and risk management, has felt the impact of GDPR significantly. Key areas of focus include obtaining explicit consent for processing personal data and maintaining comprehensive records. The right to erasure empowers individuals to request data removal, particularly when data is no longer needed for regulatory or legal purposes. Additionally, data subjects possess the right to receive their processed data in a machine-readable format. GDPR mandates informed decision-making processes, limiting automated profiling without explicit consent. To ensure compliance, strict breach notification and response protocols are crucial, emphasizing the need for preparedness with tailored incident response plans to ensure timely reporting and minimise penalties (Grima, Bezzina, & Farrugia, 2019)

Deloitte's analysis (Deloitte, 2019) emphasizes that the financial services sector has demonstrated a commendable degree of adaptability to the GDPR framework. Due to their historical adherence to stringent privacy and data privacy protection regulations set forth by financial authorities, these companies have seamlessly incorporated GDPR compliance into their operations. Their long-standing commitment to data risk management and adherence to data protection standards has led to a mature approach, distinguishing them from companies in other sectors. This sector is accustomed to rigorous regulatory scrutiny, a level of oversight not as prevalent in other industries.

Considering GDPR regulations, prioritising data privacy and protection within the UK financial services sector through robust cybersecurity measures is imperative. GDPR

bestows upon every EU citizen to the right to privacy, allowing individuals to access or request the removal of their personal data from financial institutions without external authorisation, a concept known as data portability. Additionally, GDPR mandates strict protocols for reporting data breaches within 72 hours, holding data protection officers (DPOs) accountable for providing comprehensive details about the breach. The potential consequences of a breach are substantial, with fines reaching up to €20 million (est. GBP17 million) or 4% of global turnover for severe violations. This includes failing to obtain consent for data processing or privacy breaches.

This encompasses instances such as failing to obtain consent for data processing or privacy breaches. Moreover, as IT systems play a critical role in financial firms, vendors must be held to the same standards regarding data access. GDPR imposes end-to-end accountability, requiring all support functions to comply with data protection standards. Incorporating 'Privacy by Design' principles into systems is a pivotal aspect of GDPR compliance. Failing to do so not only carry financial penalties but also poses risk to client trust and confidence, underscoring the urgency for financial institutions to prioritise GDPR compliance (Brickendon Consulting, 2017).

The analysis of GDPR's impact on the financial services sector emphasizes the critical need for robust data privacy and protection measures particularly through the integration of cybersecurity practices. The GDPR has introduced a comprehensive framework that necessitates a change in basic assumptions in how financial institutions handle and safeguard personal data. Considering the impending compliance deadline, it is imperative for financial institutions to proactively enhance their systems, not only to avoid financial penalties but also to bolster client trust and confidence in an era of heightened data privacy concerns.

2.2.7 Cloud Security in Financial Services

The widespread adoption of cloud computing architecture and infrastructure has garnered acceptance from corporations and governments globally. This change in thinking not only reduces the cost of managing physical and technical infrastructure but also makes information systems accessible to both local and global workforces. For organisations, especially in the financial services sector, cloud computing provides flexibility and accessibility to data and applications from any location. While this brings numerous advantages, it also necessitates a continuous evaluation of privacy and security frameworks. In this context, banking and financial institutions deal with sensitive data and applications, often internally developed to maintain a competitive edge. This intellectual property (IP) forms the backbone of specific business processes and objectives. However, the transition to cloud computing introduces potential risks such as data leakages and IP erosion due to remote accessibility. Consequently, the banking and financial services industry operates under stringent regulatory compliance frameworks to uphold data privacy and security of cloud architecture infrastructure on a global scale (Mahalle, Yong, Tao , & Shen, 2023).

As more companies embrace a cloud-first strategy or undergo some degree of transition to cloud infrastructure, this trend is poised to remain a top priority for C – suite executives for the near future. Beyond the technical complexities associated with this transition, several security-related concerns consistently emerge, warranting attention on internal risk registers. These concerns, each representing its own level of complexity, necessitate in-house expertise which include the following:

- Tangible concerns about data residency arise against the backdrop of heightened data regulations. Businesses, if inattentive to cloud perform terms and conditions, risk violating data retention or privacy laws across different countries.
- Although unlikely, the prospect of a major cloud provider experiencing an outage beyond their redundancy measures has prompted many companies to adopt a

multi-cloud approach, utilising services from providers like Amazon Web Services, Google, and Azure.

- The shared responsibility model across different cloud platforms poses challenges, demanding a comprehensive understanding of organisational responsibilities and the expertise to achieve a secure configuration. Many organisations have invested in training their staff on various cloud models, with larger enterprises requiring hundreds of trained personnel in different areas.

Configuration remains a central security issue in cloud adoption, with instances of data breaches stemming from improperly configured cloud observed in recent years. Despite efforts by cloud service providers to minimise such errors, they persist. The 2023 Verizon Data Breach Investigations Report (Verizon, Langlois, Pinto, Hylender, & Widdup, 2023), revealed that 22 percent of data breaches in 2019 involved cloud assets, with misconfiguration errors, many linked to the cloud, emerging as the most common type of error reported in Verizon's data (Nish, Naumaan, & Muir, 2020).

2.2.8 Encryption Dynamics in Financial Services

2.2.8.1 Cryptographic Algorithms in Financial Transactions

In the landscape of existing controls within the financial sector, one pivotal mechanism for ensuring data protection and privacy is encryption. This technology assumes a critical role in fortifying the security of financial data. By employing encryption, financial institutions establish a barrier that thwarts potential hackers from infiltrating and exploiting sensitive customer information. This includes safeguarding crucial details such as transaction histories, credit card numbers, bank account information, and passwords. The implementation of encryption stands as a fundamental measure within financial institutions. It serves to guarantee that customers' personal data remains confidential and secure throughout digital transactions (CYPHER.DOG, 2023).

2.2.8.2 Evolution of Encryption in Financial Services

Cryptographic algorithms play a pivotal role in safeguarding the security of data within financial transactions, such as ATM transactions and online banking. Among the widely adopted cryptographic algorithms, RSA has been a stalwart in ensuring data integrity and confidentiality. However, the landscape is evolving, and the financial industry, along with various sectors, is actively engaged in transitioning from RSA to Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC). This shift is driven by two primary advantages offered by ECC over RSA, 1) It achieves an equivalent security level with smaller key sizes and 2) It significantly reduces the probability of security flaws due to operational issues. This transition underscores a crucial agenda in enhancing the encryption landscape within the financial services sector (Seito, 2017).

2.2.8.3 Homomorphic Encryption for Confidential Data Sharing

Enhancing privacy and confidentiality in data sharing within financial services involves employing various techniques, and one notable method is homomorphic encryption (HE). In instances where a financial institution or its customer seeks third party engagement for data analysis, challenges may arise, such as concerns about data safety or limitations on data transfer permissions.

Homomorphic encryption serves as a solution by encrypting the data, enabling analysis without revealing the underlying information. The unique feature of HE is that decryption of the data is unnecessary, ensuring that only the intended party can comprehend the analysis results. To illustrate, consider a scenario where an individual John Doe, wishes to assess potential health risks in his medical history. Although his health insurance provider possesses the analytical capabilities, John Doe is keen on maintaining the confidentiality of his health records. With homomorphic encryption, John Doe encrypts his data and transmits it to the insurer while retaining the decryption key. The technology unit can perform the analysis while retaining the decryption key. The technology unit can

perform the analysis on the data without knowledge of the contents or results, and subsequently, both the encrypted and the outcomes returned to John Doe. He retains the ability to unlock and access the results, ensuring a secure and confidential data sharing process (Deloitte, 2019).

2.2.9 Strengthening User Verification in Financial Services

2.2.9.1 Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA)

Identifying an individual typically relies on a combination of a username and password. In security systems, it's important to differentiate between authentication and authorisation. Authentication confirms the individual's claimed identity, usually through a username and password, without specifying their access rights. Authorisation, on the other hand, involves granting individuals access to system objects based on their confirmed identity, determining their specific access rights. Financial Institutions face risks with traditional authentication methods, necessitating a shift to multi-factor authentication (MFA) (Mohamed, 2014).

Three globally recognised authentication methods include token-supported authentication, utilising key cards, bank cards, and smart cards, sometimes incorporating knowledge-based techniques for enhanced security. Biometric-supported authentication, employing features like fingerprints, iris scans, and facial recognition, faces limited adoption due to cost and slower, sometimes unreliable identification processes. Knowledge-supported authentication is the most widely used method, encompassing both text-based and image-based passwords. Image-based techniques further divide into recognition-based, where users identify pre-registered images, and recall-based, requiring users to reproduce a registered pattern created during the registration process (Prasad & Aithal, 2018).

Despite advancements in ATM hardware and payment software by many banks and credit unions to thwart sophisticated fraud attempts, concerns persist. In 2018, 14 out of 21 European countries reported incidents of ATM card skimming (E.A.S.T, 2023). The escalating pace at which hackers are advancing poses a significant challenge, with virtually no authentication technique immune to compromise (Lala, Aworinde, & Ekpe, 2020).

Engaging in transactions with unauthorised or inaccurately identified individuals in an online setting poses the risk of financial losses and damage to reputation. Customers relying on online financial services seek assurance that their financial institutions prioritise the safeguarding of confidential personal information and account access. Consequently, financial and business institutions must enhance both security measures and customer confidence to encourage the adoption of their online brokerage channels. Implementing multi-factor authentication and risk evaluation services becomes imperative to enhance security without adding complexity for users. Multi-Factor Authentication & Security applications provide swiftly deployable solutions that can be tailored to address the most stringent online security requirements (Mohamed, 2014)

2.2.9.2 Privileged Account Management

Privileged Account Management (PAM) constitutes a crucial aspect of identity and Access Management, with a primary focus on overseeing and regulating the utilisation of privileged accounts. These accounts encompass various categories such as local and domain administrative accounts, emergency accounts, application management, and service accounts. Due to their potent nature, offering elevated and often restricted access to vital IT resources, these accounts become prime targets for attackers and malicious insiders. Consequently, it becomes imperative to closely monitor, audit, control, and manage the usage of privileged accounts. Numerous organisations, particularly those in the financial sector, encounter difficulties in effectively handling privileged accounts. Numerous organisations, particularly those in the financial sector, encounter difficulties in

effectively handling privileged accounts. Recognising the potential threat, the Federal Financial Institutions Examination Council (FFIEC) Cyber assessment Tool (CAT) emphasises the necessity for stringent control over privileged accounts (Banoczi, Perper, & Prince, 2017).

In contemporary financial institutions, employees require access to a diverse array of applications, resources, and systems to ensure seamless business operations and enhance customer interactions. Typically, access is facilitated through user accounts, commonly secured by usernames and passwords. However, not all accounts are equal; some, known as privileged accounts, possess authorisation for actions beyond the scope of ordinary accounts. These privileged accounts grant elevated and often unrestricted access to crucial corporate resources and essential systems, going beyond what a standard user account allows. IT administrators and managers utilise these privileged accounts for mission-critical tasks such as maintenance, system management, and access control. The fundamental risk associated with privileged accounts lies in the potential for significant harm to business operations if they are misused for malicious or erroneous purposes.

Recognising the value of privileged accounts, malicious external attackers specifically target them to maximise access to an organisation's data, applications, and infrastructure, thereby increasing the risk of data breaches, espionage, sabotage, or ransom. Additionally, these malicious actors may exploit privileged accounts to circumvent or disable other cybersecurity measures or legal compliance protections safeguarding critical systems or data. The potential threat associated with privileged accounts extends beyond external malicious actors. While occurrences are rare, there have been cases of discontented employees exploiting either their own or their colleagues' privileged accounts for harmful intentions, such as extracting sensitive data, engaging in industrial sabotage, or establishing technical vulnerabilities for subsequent exploitation. Additionally, less wicked situations involve employees who would have good intentions, while using their privileged accounts, inadvertently make mistakes that result in

substantial disruptions impacting business operations and customer satisfaction (Waltermire, et al., 2018).

2.2.9.3 Innovative Approaches to User Authentication and Access Control in Financial Institutions

Financial Institutions are increasingly recognising the paramount importance of user verification and access control in the realm of cybersecurity. This acknowledgement is emphasised by the growing adoption of advanced Identity and Access Management (IAM) solutions. IAM tools, traditionally serving as gatekeepers, have evolved to encompass sophisticated functions such as defining key access levels, monitoring user activities, and swiftly responding to security breaches. This section introduces the key trends within the financial sector focusing on integrating IAM solutions to streamline data protection efforts, control costs, and explore innovative methods, like utilising smartphones, to enhance cybersecurity measures. Among these trends, the transformation of smartphones into security tokens is gaining prominence, exemplified by leading banks leveraging text alerts and software-based solutions for enhancing protection, particularly in the realm of online transactions (Ejanthkar, Vaidyanath, & Sullivan, 2012).

2.2.9 Cybersecurity Training and Awareness in Financial Services

2.2.9.1 Addressing Fraud Risk through Comprehensive Training

Recent studies highlight that relying solely on technology is inadequate in delivering effective solutions for IT security challenges. Currently, there has been limited emphasis on the training and education of end users regarding how to effectively manage and defend against malicious IT threats such as phishing attacks (Alghamdi, 2017). Every individual is susceptible to the threat of falling victim to fraud, whether as a private person or as a customer of various entities such as banks, insurance companies, mobile operators, and government services. Addressing fraud risk comprehensively requires

more than just incorporating fraud-related processes into daily operations and deploying detection and prevention tools. Typically, the most vulnerable point is the individual, whether an employee or a customer, particularly those lacking sufficient knowledge. Hence, it is crucial to supplement the measures with initiatives focused on awareness and education (Skula, Bohacik, & Zabovsky, 2020).

2.2.9.2 Strengthening Phishing Education Initiatives

Phishing stands out as a predominant social attack affecting businesses, contributing to more than 75% of security breaches today. Given the inherent limitations of cybersecurity solutions to completely thwart such attacks, it becomes imperative to fortify existing phishing education initiatives. This is crucial for comprehending the nature of these attacks and ensuring individual protection, considering the protracted and costly process of mitigating their consequences, which can potentially compromise the entire infrastructure network. Consequently, organisations function cohesively as a unified team, adhering to established regulations for comprehensive protection. Furthermore, establishing a systematic approach for regular attack notifications, such as through mass mailing and information dissemination via available sources, is recommended.

2.2.9.3 Dynamic Phishing Awareness Programs

In addition to structured annual or semi-annual cybersecurity training, companies in the financial sector should carry out dynamic phishing awareness programs. These programs, offering immediate feedback usage, include innovative solutions like the KASAP (Kaspersky Automated Security Awareness Platform). This platform provides training, testing, and assistance from system administrators, allowing for the distribution of legitimate phishing messages to enhance overall cyber literacy (Alimzhanova & Spanova, 2023).

2.2.9.4 User Awareness and Protection Measures

When users are unaware that their personal information is actively targeted by cybercriminals, they may struggle to recognise phishing threats. Such users might overlook essential precautions while engaging in online activities. Phishers find it appealing when their targets lack awareness of their organisation's policies. In some cases, customers may not be familiar with the procedures to follow when contacted about fraud investigations or account maintenance issues. Customers unaware of organisational procedures are more susceptible to phishing attempts, even if they possess technical knowledge. Activities such as DDoS attacks, spamming, and electronic surveillance are technically challenging but have been demonstrated by sophisticated criminals. While customers recognise the danger of these scams, phishers continuously develop more technically sophisticated tactics to enhance the effectiveness and deception of phishing scams (Alghamdi, 2017).

2.2.9.5 Evolving Security Practices and Challenges in the Financial Services Sector

However, there seems to be a literature gap, with a predominant focus on preventive technical approaches in the existing discussions. Conversely, efforts in security and user training have predominantly centred around web-based education concerning email phishing attacks, overlooking other forms of such threats. Recent research highlights that relying solely on technology is insufficient to address IT security issues adequately. There has been limited attention given to training and educating end users on effectively handling malicious IT threats, such as phishing attacks, overlooking other forms of such threats.

Security practices within the financial services sector are evolving, with executives and boards demonstrating a heightened commitment to cybersecurity investment and the implementation of advanced protocols. Despite this progress, Chief Information Officers (CISOs) need to consistently reassess their risk assessment methodologies, adapting to

the ever-improving capabilities of cyber adversaries to maintain a proactive stance. Maturity assessments have been a preferred tool for CISOs to guide spending priorities. However, there is a growing demand from CEO's for more sophisticated risk quantification methods that align with broader business risks. The rapid acceleration of digitisation, remote work, and virtual customer engagement, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, necessitates a re-evaluation of legacy cybersecurity practices by CISOs. This is particularly crucial due to the enduring presence of certain threats, ranging from phishing and malware to deficiencies in extended enterprise controls and insider threats. As remote work and digital transformation become enduring trends, financial services organisations must intensify their focus on embracing cloud technologies, securing the extended enterprise, ensuring a trusted customer experience, establishing resilient operations, and addressing control gaps. This comprehensive approach involves adopting advanced incident detection and response capabilities, strengthening perimeter controls, enhancing risk identification methods, and implementing targeted employee education initiatives. While recognising that there is no one-size-fits-all solution applicable across the industry, the universal truth remains that evolving risks will necessitate continuous adaptation and innovative responses (Deloitte, 2022).

Figure 16 - These are steps that are recommended to fortify data protection in the financial services industry (Deloitte, 2022).

2.3 Horizon Scanning in Financial Cybersecurity

2.3.1 Quantum Computing: The Impacts and Opportunities in Financial Services

The advent of quantum computing is on the horizon, presenting significant implications for both the global economy and the financial system. The rapid progress in quantum computing development brings forth a dual impact-offering substantial advantages while also introducing potential risks. Quantum computers have the capacity to transform industries and disciplines that demand extensive computational capabilities, encompassing activities such as modelling financial markets, developing innovative medicines and vaccines, enhancing artificial intelligence, and establishing a novel and secure mode of communication through quantum internet. However, their emergence also raises concerns as they could compromise existing encryption algorithms, posing a threat to the security of various financial aspects like mobile banking, e-commerce, fintech, digital currencies, and online information exchange. Despite ongoing efforts in advancing quantum-safe encryption, there is still work to be done. Financial institutions are urged to proactively prepare for the impending cryptographic transition by evaluating prospective and retrospective risks associated with quantum computers, conducting an inventory of their cryptographic algorithms-particularly public keys-and fostering cryptographic agility to enhance overall cybersecurity resilience (Deodoro, Gorbanyov, Malaika, & Sedik, 2021).

In the financial services sector, numerous computationally challenging issues emerge across asset management, investment banking, retail, and corporate banking. Quantum computing has the potential to revolutionise the approach to solving these complex problems. The availability of the first noisy quantum devices, built upon principles of quantum mechanics and publicly accessible today, has sparked active research on the applicability of quantum computing in finance and the demonstration of Quantum

Advantage in initial applications. According to (Egger, et al., 2020), the financial services sector is inherently forward-looking, consistently seeking to harness emerging technologies for enhanced profitability. This industry broadly encompasses three vertical sectors as illustrated in [Figure 17](#) below.

Banking	Financial Markets	Insurance
Monetary Authorities Retail Banking	Commodities Stock Exchanges	Health Insurance Property & Casualty Insurance
Commercial Banking	Bond Markets	Life Insurance & Annuity
Investment Banking Non-Banking FIs	Money Markets Derivatives	Reinsurance

Figure 17 - Segments of the financial Sector (Egger, et al., 2020).

- 1. Banking:** Primarily offering bank accounts, investments, and loans to both commercial and retail customers, the banking sector experiences challenges such as balancing cash with interest rates and mitigating threats related to liquidity, fraud, money laundering, and nonperforming loans (NPLs).
- 2. Financial Markets:** Focused on future gains and the trading of assets through various entities like dealers, exchanges, brokers, and clearing houses, financial markets encounter challenges related to managing geographic time zones, immediacy needs and counterparty risk.
- 3. Insurance:** Encompassing health insurance, automobile and property insurance, life insurance and annuity, and reinsurance, the insurance sector faces the primary challenge of maximising premiums while effectively managing risks associated with unplanned events, such as catastrophes or market crashes.

The ongoing digital financial services revolution is profoundly disrupting the industry, ushering in new players that pose a threat to the existing status quo. FinTech’s and InsurTechs bring innovative digital style offerings, RegTech introduces automated regulation processes, and competition emerges from other industry corporations equipped to provide digital financial services to their customers. Additionally, clients now

demand personalised offerings based on their behavioural data, such as tailored insurance premiums linked to life events or targeted loan offers for specific customer segments. The regulatory environment further complicates operations by necessitating risk mitigation and strict compliance. These evolving trends have given rise to novel financial services experiences, including seamless global supply chains in trade finance asset management, Artificial Intelligence (AI) augmentation facilitating trusted decision - making in investment banking, and banking platforms evolving into finance “as-a-service” (Egger, et al., 2020).

Leveraging quantum computing for financial challenges, particularly in dealing with constrained and uncertain models, holds numerous benefits for early investors and users (Ahmed, Aljarbouh, Donepudi, & Choi, 2020). Imagine the capability to compute and identify adaptable arbitrage opportunities that may be imperceptible to rivals and competitors. Moreover, quantum computing has the potential to provide specific advantages, including improved customer engagement utilising behavioural data, enhanced compliance, and swifter responses to market volatility (Ganapathy, 2021).

Figure 18 - Benefits of Quantum Computing in Finance (Ganapathy, 2021).

As the financial industry explores the possibilities of quantum computing, it's crucial to acknowledge the ongoing progress in quantum-safe encryption. While the transition to quantum-safe encryption is still underway, financial institutions must proactively take measures to prepare for this cryptographic shift. This involves assessing potential risks posed by quantum computers, both in the future and retroactively. Institutions should

conduct a comprehensive inventory of their cryptographic algorithms, with special attention to public keys. Additionally, building cryptographic agility is essential to enhance overall cybersecurity resilience in anticipation of quantum advancements (Deodoro, Gorbanyov, Malaika, & Sedik, 2021).

The financial services sector has witnessed an increased adoption of AI, particularly with the widespread use of Predictive AI, while Generative AI is in the early stages of emergence. Although there were initial reservations about adopting Generative AI, there is a growing recognition of its potential, prompting institutions to contemplate integrating it alongside Predictive AI. As risk management capabilities advance, the adoption of Generative AI is anticipated to escalate, potentially evolving into a significant competitive advantage within the finance sector.

The financial services sector is experiencing a rapid increase in AI adoption, propelled by advancements in predictive analytics and machine learning. Numerous institutions have already implemented Predictive AI systems across diverse functions such as credit scoring, fraud detection, chatbots for customer support and forecasting economic trends. Despite this widespread adoption, most firms anticipate that the adoption of Predictive AI will continue to expand, particularly in tandem with the integration of Generative AI. Common applications of Predictive AI include fraud detection, risk modelling, Know Your Customer (KYC), and document authentication. For instance, tools for outlier detection can pinpoint potentially fraudulent transactions by comparing them to historical payments. These outlier transactions are subject to direct blocking or are highlighted for client review, allowing them to approve or reject the payments as needed.

2.3.2 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT): The challenges and opportunities in the financial services sector

Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) stands at the forefront of innovation, presenting a dynamic and swiftly evolving approach to recording and disseminating data across multiple ledgers or data stores. This cutting-edge technology facilitates the seamless recording, sharing, and synchronisation of transactions and data within a distributed network encompassing diverse participants. Within the realm of DLT, the 'blockchain' emerges as a distinctive data structure employed in specific distributed ledgers. Operating through the organisation of data in "blocks" interconnected in a digital 'chain', blockchain harnesses cryptographic and algorithmic methodologies to immutably record and synchronise data throughout the network. Delving further into this landscape, Distributed Ledgers (DLs) epitomise a specific implementation within the broader category of shared ledgers. These shared records of data, existing among various parties, can take form of a single ledger with layered permissions for a distributed ledger – a network of multiple ledgers maintained by nodes dispersed across the system (Natarajan, Krause, & Gradstein, 2017).

One of the primary catalysts propelling the wave of innovation in blockchain lies in its potential to transition from centralised and proprietary ecosystems to decentralised and mutualised counterparts. Specifically for financial entities, notable banks, this shift implies an elevated risk of disintermediation and poses a potential threat to certain activities that were traditionally coordinated by banks as central coordinators. However, the growing interest of financial institutions in Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) extends beyond concerns about disintermediation. It reflects an increasing realisation that this technology could usher in a wave of transformations and innovations that would be advantageous for both financial institutions themselves and their clients, whether individuals or corporations (Collomb & Sok, 2016). Despite the widespread attention and acknowledgement, various applications of blockchain technology have raised apprehensions. Instances such as distributed autonomous organisations (DAOs) functioning on blockchain infrastructures

or initial coin offerings (ICOs) employing existing digital tokens for fundraising have encountered scrutiny. Numerous Bitcoin-like digital currencies have been labelled as “Ponzi schemes” or, at most, deemed “solutions in search of a problem.” Certain critics have issued warnings that the adoption of such a technological shift might not only draw criminal activities but could also potentially lead to an increase in authoritarianism (Werbach, 2018).

Opinions on the legitimacy and effectiveness of blockchain vary widely. Even those who strongly support the ‘blockchain revolution’ acknowledge that the most significant challenge for growth of distributed ledgers is governance. It has been stated that any controversy surrounding blockchain today revolves around these governance issues. In contrast to established foundational technologies like the internet, governed by well-established international organisations (such as IETF, Internet Governance Forum, W3C, ICANN, Internet Society, etc), current blockchain platforms and cryptocurrency communities are often characterised as chaotic, lacking the structure needed to reach consensus, coordinate action, and resolve differences (Tapscott & Tapscott, 2016).

Naturally, this has the potential to hinder the widespread acceptance of the technology and impede the development of future blockchain applications. More crucially, it introduces substantial risks for users and raises mounting apprehension among regulators, particularly within financial services, where any compromise to the stability and trust in the fiscal landscape is a matter of utmost significance (Zachariadis, Hileman, & Susan V. Scott, 2019).

2.3.3 Artificial Intelligence: Friend or Foe in Financial Cybersecurity – analysing the potential risks and benefits of AI in safeguarding financial data.

The advent of machine learning marks a notable transformation within the financial services sector. Finance, inherently centred around data, constitutes a multifaceted domain integrating insights from diverse fields like mathematics, statistics, psychology,

and linguistics. This complexity poses challenges in addressing day to day issues within finance, including errors stemming from human mistakes. Leveraging machine learning, the financial sector has embraced a wide array of applications, harnessing its exceptional capabilities to navigate these challenges effectively (Kaur, Kumar, & Kaur, 2023).

We all engage in transactions as consumers, defined legally as natural persons involved in legal dealings with entrepreneurs unrelated to their business professional activities. In various transactions, including those in the financial market, consumers increasingly interact with artificial intelligence (AI) systems, which have seen rapid development. The integration of AI into consumer transactions raises concerns, especially considering that consumers, being non-professionals in economic turnover, are often the weaker party. Transactions involving consumers exhibit information and market power asymmetry, with entrepreneurs holding an advantage due to their professional knowledge, experience, and market information. Consumer protection laws aim to address this market imbalance caused by asymmetry between consumers and entrepreneurs. The rise of artificial intelligence introduces new challenges and potential threats to consumers, prompting considerations within various branches of law, particularly consumer protection law. The evolving landscape of AI development raises questions about whether it poses risks to consumers and if amendments to consumer protection laws are necessary for enhanced safeguarding. Defining “artificial intelligence” itself is a complex task, broadly understood as a computer science branch dealing with constructing intelligent machines and algorithms (Nizioł, 2021).

In the dynamic realm of finance, banks and insurance enterprises navigate a complex and fiercely competitive landscape, marked by substantial pressure to adapt and thrive. The ongoing transformation is paramount for survival in this ever-evolving market. Within this context, the preservation of customer loyalty takes centre stage, encompassing elements like satisfaction, trust, commitment, and perceived value. Tech gurus like Google, Facebook, and Apple have effectively demonstrated that steadfast commitment to customers, coupled with the strategic utilisation of modern technologies, can redefine the processes within the financial services sector. However traditional financial service

providers often struggle to provide the requisite flexibility and innovation to meet the diverse needs of their clientele (Kruse, Wunderlich, & Beck, 2019).

This gap has paved way for the disruptive force known as FinTech, embraced as a game changer capable of challenging and reshaping traditional financial markets. Operating with cutting-edge technologies, FinTech entities distinguish themselves by not adhering to legacy architectures. Through streamlined and agile processes, these innovative companies achieve heightened customer orientation, reduced costs, and an accelerated pace of innovation. Predominantly entrepreneurial, FinTechs have spearheaded significant breakthroughs across various domains, including payment systems, wealth management, lending, and crowdfunding. Furthermore, their influence extends to catalysing the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning within the financial services sector. The emergence of digitally native FinTechs, deeply rooted in customer centric business models, compels traditional financial market players to undergo transformative changes. At the nexus of customer interactions and institutional operations, the continuous generation and analysis of data present immense potential for evaluation and the development of innovative products and services (Kruse, Wunderlich, & Beck, 2019).

Figure 19 - Anticipated Impact of widespread AI adoption on overall market risk (Ryll, et al., 2020).

Figure 19 is a representation derived from an investigation done by (Ryll, et al., 2020) pertaining to perceptions to potential risks that could impact the financial services sector. As illustrated in the diagram, there are significant variations in perspectives between

those who perceive AI as predominantly consolidating force in the industry and those who view it as primarily disruptive. Individuals emphasising consolidation express concerns about the emergence of shared operational vulnerabilities and critical points of failure in the financial services industry. These concerns include potential issues like widespread data breaches, cybersecurity threats, or excessive dependence on a limited number of vendors. Conversely, those endorsing disruption as the prevailing force concentrate on challenges to the market's capacity for precise risk assessment and pricing, encompassing factors such as market uncertainty, biases, and systematic risks.

As we navigate the landscape of AI within the financial sector, it is crucial to acknowledge the potential pitfalls that arise when transitioning from theory to real world application. In practical scenarios, AI systems, while seemingly flawless in controlled environments, can exhibit unpredictability and unreliability. Unlike human decision-makers, algorithms lack higher-level assessments, intuition, or ethical considerations. The absence of "common sense" and an inherent ethical override poses a myriad of legal concerns, particularly in the context of fairness requirements outlined by GDPR. This concern is further exacerbated when AI algorithms make decisions that display biases or discrimination, potentially violating the overarching principles of fairness enshrined in data protection regulations (Artzt & Dung, 2022).

Navigating the ethical and legal considerations surrounding AI in the financial sector leads us to the AI act, which imposes specific requirements on high-risk AI systems. These requirements are designed to ensure responsible AI deployment and mitigate potential risks. The key obligations encompass establishing a comprehensive risk management system, providing transparent and bias-free training data, creating technical documentation for compliance, maintaining traceability through automatic logs, enabling human oversight to minimise risks, and ensuring accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity. It's noteworthy that the AI Act introduces more detailed and specific requirements compared to the GDPR. For instance, it places emphasis on preventing bias and discrimination in training, validation, and testing data. Additionally, the Act

mandates human oversight, a critical aspect often overlooked in automated decision-making processes. This contrasts with the GDPR, which focuses on the fairness of processing without delving into the specifics of AI system oversight. As we delve into the nuanced requirements set forth by the AI Act, it becomes evident that it establishes a more targeted framework for addressing the unique challenges posed by high-risk AI systems in the financial sector (Artzt & Dung, 2022).

In summary, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning in the financial sector presents transformative opportunities alongside emerging challenges. As the industry adopts these technologies to enhance efficiency and innovation, concerns arise regarding biases, discrimination, and potential cybersecurity threats. The FinTech disruption adds complexity to the regulatory landscape, emphasising the need for adaptive frameworks.

The perceived impact of widespread AI adoption on market risk, depicted in [figure 19](#), reveals varying industry perspectives on its consolidating or disruptive influence. The practical application of AI introduces legal and ethical considerations, prompting the implementation of the AI Act with stringent requirements for high-risk AI systems.

Navigating this horizon requires aligning technological advancements with robust cybersecurity measures. This ensures the responsible deployment of AI, mitigating risks, and enhancing data privacy and protection in the financial services sector.

Chapter 3 Approach and Methodology

3.1 Research Methodology

The research methodology involved a systematic approach that integrated insights from literature review, expert consultation, and alignment with research objectives. The research design for this dissertation adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative methods. This approach allowed for a comprehensive exploration of the research problem. It also facilitates a deeper understanding of the complexities within the UK financial services sector. The strategy was derived from “the review of literature and the future of the new research paradigm” by (Migiro & Magangi, 2011).

3.1.1 Qualitative Phase

The qualitative phase involved in-depth interviews with key industry experts, cybersecurity professionals, data privacy officers, and other stakeholders within the financial services sector. Interviews are the most frequently used qualitative methods and they allowed for the data collected to be rich. The interviews included focus group interviews and were followed by a few structured interviews which helped provide valuable insights on the current risk, existing controls, and perspectives on emerging technologies (Alsaawi, 2014).

3.1.2 Quantitative phase – Survey Methodology

Conducting surveys stands out as a crucial aspect of measurement in the field of applied research (Kuter & Yilmaz, 2001). To delve into the specifics of the Quantitative phase, readers are encouraged to consult the detailed questionnaire presented in [Appendix E](#).

Objective

The questionnaire was designed to critically evaluate the current state and effectiveness of data privacy and cybersecurity within the UK's financial services sector. It aimed to identify areas of strength and potential gaps, especially in relation to GDPR compliance and the evolving cybersecurity landscape.

The process of designing and executing the survey involved the following steps:

1. Aligning the questionnaire to the objectives and the research goals of assessing data privacy, identifying vulnerabilities, and proposing solutions within the UK financial services sector.
2. Ensuring a comprehensive representation of stakeholders by incorporating a diverse range of job titles, including cybersecurity experts, compliance officers, IT professionals, business managers and senior management. The questions were purposefully designed to capture perspectives from various organisation levels, enhancing the richness of the data collection process.
3. Questions specifically aimed at identifying challenges and concerns faced by the industry, as well as measures and technologies in place to address the challenges were posed.
4. Questions focused on assessing the perception of third-party vendor risks, reflecting the importance of external factors on data privacy and cybersecurity were posed.

5. Likert scale questions were used to gauge respondents' perceptions on various aspects, such as confidence levels, satisfaction, effectiveness, and alignment.
6. Administering the questionnaire to professionals within the financial services sector covering confidence levels, perceptions, and practices related to data privacy and cybersecurity.
7. Electronic Distribution using Microsoft Forms facilitated efficient data collection and compilation.
8. Executing the survey by sharing it with industry professionals and sharing the link on professional social media platforms such as Linked In.
9. Analysing the gathered data which is discussed in the next section.

The survey was comprehensive, covering a range of pertinent topics. It began with questions assessing general confidence in current data privacy measures, then gradually moved towards more specific areas such as the effectiveness of GDPR implementation, the frequency and quality of cybersecurity training, and the integration of technology in data protection strategies.

Questions were also aligned to uncover practical challenges faced by organisations, including the management of sensitive data, compliance with legal requirements, and response to cybersecurity incidents.

3.2 Data Analysis

3.2.1 Qualitative Data Analysis

In line with the interpretative and subjective nature of qualitative research, the analysis of the interview data conducted via Microsoft Teams, involves a deep immersion into the participants' perspectives. (Lacey & Luff, 2009) aptly describe qualitative research as an intimate and engaged process, acknowledging the researcher's active involvement in shaping the interpretation of the findings. A subject-related analysis was employed to analyse qualitative data from interviews. This approach involved identifying patterns, themes, and trends within the responses, providing a rich and nuanced understanding of the risk landscape and current controls.

3.2.2 Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the questionnaire was analysed using Microsoft forms and the quantitative findings were interpreted and summarised, providing a clear overview of the participants' perceptions and practices. The results of the quantitative data were reported, providing a comprehensive overview of the findings, and facilitating a clear and meaningful understanding of the survey responses. This quantitative data analysis approach ensures a rigorous and comprehensive exploration of the survey data, allowing for nuanced interpretation of the research findings (Lacey & Luff, 2009).

3.2.3 Integration of Data

The qualitative and quantitative findings were integrated to develop a comprehensive understanding of the risk landscape and existing controls within the UK financial services sector.

3.2.4 Comparative Analysis

Comparative analysis was conducted to identify correlations between qualitative insights from interviews and quantitative data from the questionnaire, contributing to a holistic interpretation of the research problem.

3.3 Literature Review

A thorough literature review was conducted to explore the risk landscape, the existing cybersecurity controls and horizon scanning of data privacy and protection in the financial services sector providing a comprehensive foundation for understanding the challenges at hand to develop a cybersecurity framework to address these challenges.

3.4 Expert Consultation

In the pursuit of comprehensive insights, one-on-one interviews and expert consultations were conducted with cybersecurity experts in the financial services sector, notably including a Chief Information Security Officer (CISO) from a prominent financial institution. This deliberate engagement strategy sought to unravel valuable perspectives on the current risk landscape, discuss the effectiveness of existing cybersecurity controls, and to explore the implications of emerging advancements on data privacy within the financial services sector.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

3.5.1 Informed Consent

Participants in both qualitative and quantitative phases were provided with clear information about the research's purpose, nature, and confidentiality. Informed consent was obtained, ensuring compliance with GDPR regulations. This ensured that all collected information was used solely for the purpose of this research.

3.5.2 Anonymity and Confidentiality

All collected data was treated with utmost confidentiality. Participants' identities were protected through anonymisation and secure storage of data.

3.5.3 Limitations

The study acknowledges certain limitations, including potential bias in participant responses and evolving nature of the cybersecurity landscape.

Chapter 4 Legal, Ethical, Social and Professional Issues (LESPI)

This chapter delves into the complex dimensions of the legal, ethical, social, and professional issues within the research. It indicates how the research is anchored by the principles of GDPR and it provides interesting insights into societal perspectives and professional challenges.

4.1 Legal Considerations

The research methodology thoroughly followed the guidelines outlined in the GDPR, with a paramount focus on obtaining informed consent from every participant. Recognising the dynamic shifts within the cybersecurity landscape, the study emphasises the imperative for continuous legal evaluations to seamlessly align with and respond to emerging regulations.

4.2 Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from all participants, clarifying the research's purpose, and ensuring confidentiality. Anonymity was maintained through data anonymisation and secure storage. The study recognises the potential for bias in participant responses and emphasises ongoing ethical evaluations in the face of evolving cybersecurity challenges.

4.3 Social Implications

The study's revelations extend beyond the realm of research, holding noteworthy social ramifications. The observed moderate confidence in existing data privacy measures points to a societal recognition of challenges, highlighting a collective understanding of the ever-evolving landscape of cybersecurity threats. The sector's tendency for technology-driven solutions not only signifies a societal eagerness to adopt innovation for heightened security but also prompts thinking about the careful balance between relying on technology and considering the human side of cybersecurity in society.

4.4 Professional Issues

While exploring the complex landscape of the UK financial services sector, professional considerations took centre stage. Collaborating with industry experts and professionals was pivotal, ensuring that the research design resonated with the industry's requirements. The inclusion of diverse job titles in the survey sought to gather insights from different organisational levels in both the financial and cybersecurity sectors, enriching the depth of the data collection process. The study acknowledges the professional challenges tied to aligning with the GDPR compliance and the dynamic cybersecurity landscape, highlighting the demand for clearer guidance and dedicated resources.

4.5 Conclusion

Embarking on a thorough examination, this chapter delves into the multifaceted realms of legal, ethical, social, and professional issues pertinent to the research. Beyond a scholarly undertaking, the objective is not only to enrich academic understanding but to unveil pragmatic approaches to enhance data privacy and cybersecurity. Within the ever-evolving domain of the UK financial services sector, this exploration seeks to offer insights

that bridge theoretical insights with actionable strategies for a more secure and resilient future.

Chapter 5 Detailed Analysis of Results

5.1 Evaluation of the Data Collection Results

The analysis delves into various facets of cybersecurity, unveiling insights gathered from a comprehensive survey/questionnaire. From the nuanced perceptions of data privacy measures to challenges posed by evolving threats, each section provides a glimpse into the current state of the sector. These findings offer valuable perspectives that can inform strategies for enhancing cybersecurity frameworks and strengthening defences in an era marked by technological advancements and sophisticated cyber threats. The subsequent sections reveal findings from the perspectives of Forty-One (41) respondents, providing an objective perspective on the current landscape.

5.1.1 Confidence in Current Data Privacy Measures

- The moderate level of confidence expressed by many respondents suggests an awareness of the ongoing challenges in data privacy. This indicates a recognition of the evolving nature of cybersecurity threats and the need for continuous improvement in protective measures.

5.1.2 Perception of Cybersecurity Preparedness

- The consensus on the need for stronger cybersecurity frameworks points to a gap between current practices and the ideal state of preparedness. It reflects a sector grappling with rapid technological changes and increasingly sophisticated cyber threats.

5.1.3 GDPR Compliance

- The responses highlight a complex relationship with GDPR compliance. While its importance is recognised, the challenges in full adherence suggest difficulties in navigating the regulatory landscape. This may indicate a need for clearer guidance or more resources dedicated to compliance.

5.1.4 Frequency of Cybersecurity Training

- The varied responses regarding training frequency emphasise a potential inconsistency in how cybersecurity education is prioritised across the sector. Regular and comprehensive training is crucial in building a resilient workforce capable of responding to evolving threats.

5.1.5 Challenges in Data Security

- Identified challenges such as technological advancements and employee compliance emphasise the multifaceted nature of cybersecurity. It suggests that addressing these challenges requires a holistic approach, combining technological, human, and procedural elements.

5.1.6 Role of Technology in Data Protection

- The inclination towards technology-driven solutions signifies a sector eager to embrace innovation for enhanced security. However, this also raises questions about the balance between technological reliance and the human elements of

cybersecurity.

5.1.7 Incident Response and Third-Party Vendor Risk Management

- Responses indicate a need for more structured incident response strategies and thorough risk assessments of third-party vendors. This points to an area that could significantly impact overall data security if not adequately addressed.

5.1.8 Charts representing the summary of results from the survey.

The following figures encapsulate a summary of the outcomes derived from the survey/questionnaire that was disseminated.

Figure 20 - Screenshot of Total Respondents and Roles of Latest Responses

In [figure 21](#), most respondents are confident in their organisation's data privacy measures, and generally view the UK financial services sector's readiness to handle cybersecurity threats as positive.

Figure 21 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 2 & 3

Figure 22 depicts that regulatory frameworks like GDPR are generally perceived as addressing the challenges faced by the financial services sector to a moderate extent, and cybersecurity training occurs most commonly on a yearly basis.

Figure 22 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 4 & 5

In [figure 23](#) it shows that a strong majority agree that technological advancements are crucial for enhancing data privacy and cybersecurity and believe that customer awareness significantly contributes to the cybersecurity posture of the financial services sector.

Figure 23 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 6 & 7

The charts from the summary of responses from question 8 and 9 depict that most find current incident response plans to be effective in minimising data breaches, and there is moderate satisfaction with the state of data privacy regulations in the UK financial services sector.

Figure 24 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 8 & 9

The charts which represent the summary of responses to question 10 & 11 depict that there is a consensus that current data privacy regulations align somewhat well with the evolving technological landscape, and awareness of the financial and reputational risks associated with data privacy is high among senior leadership.

Figure 25 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 10 & 11

The chart representation of the summary of responses from question 12 & 13 depict that external third-party vendors and partners are seen as posing a significant risk to data privacy and cybersecurity, with cyber-attacks and employee unawareness being the key challenges.

Figure 26 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 12 & 13

The summary of responses to question 14 & 15 show that regular security audits and employee training are the primary methods used to ensure data's confidentiality, integrity, and security, with encryption being the most common control for protecting transferred PII.

Figure 27 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 14 & 15

The summary of responses to question 16 demonstrates that encryption and security information and event management are the most implemented cybersecurity measures to protect customer data.

Figure 28 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 16

The summary of responses from question 17 & 18 show that bank account details and customer account information are the most collected types of sensitive financial data, and most organisations have control procedures to restrict access to PII.

Figure 29 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 17 & 18

Figure 30 shows that many organisations employ a combination of data protection policies and secure communication practices to ensure data privacy compliance.

Figure 30 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 19

Figure 31 demonstrates that most organisations have a documented incident response, with most updating it annually.

Figure 31 - Summary of Questionnaire Results, Question 20

The chart which represents the summary of responses to question 21 indicates that compliance with industry standards is considered the most crucial factor when evaluating third-party vendors for security risk management.

Figure 32 - Summary of Questionnaire Results question 21

5.2 Overall Evaluation

The findings provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of data privacy and cybersecurity in the UK financial services sector. While there is clear recognition of the importance and challenges associated with cybersecurity and GDPR compliance, the results reveal gaps in training, policy consistency, and incident management. The sector appears to be at a critical juncture, needing to bolster its efforts in these areas to effectively navigate the increasingly complex cybersecurity landscape.

These insights are valuable for developing targeted improvements and strategies to enhance data privacy and cybersecurity in the sector. They also highlight the importance of a continuous, dynamic approach to cybersecurity, adapting to new threats and changes in the regulatory environment.

Chapter 6 Summary of Findings

In this section, we analyse the findings from the survey and the literature review. By combining real-world data from a thorough questionnaire survey with insights from academic research, we focus on improving data privacy and protection in the UK financial services sector through cybersecurity. This synthesis aims to connect practical experiences with academic research, providing a comprehensive understanding of the current cybersecurity landscape. The goal is to uncover insights into the effectiveness of current practices, identify challenges, and explore strategies for strengthening data privacy and security in the ever-changing digital world. This integrated approach offers a unique perspective crucial for developing strong and flexible cybersecurity frameworks in the financial services sector.

6.1 Comparative Analysis

The comparative analysis begins by contrasting survey findings on confidence in current data privacy measures against literature discussing the evolving nature of cybersecurity threats. It reveals a correlation between theoretical concepts of rapid technological changes and practical observations or varying confidence levels in organisational cybersecurity measures.

Next it examines the perceptions of preparedness against cybersecurity threats. The survey indicates mixed views, aligning with literature that emphasises the need for adaptive strategies to counteract advanced cyber threats. Regarding regulatory frameworks, the synthesis contrasts survey responses highlighting the need for sector-specific guidelines with literature advocating for dynamic, flexible regulatory approaches. The frequency of cybersecurity training in organisations, as revealed in the survey, is compared with the literature's emphasis on continuous learning, underscoring the importance of regular training in mitigating human error-related breaches.

The role of technology in enhancing data privacy, as perceived in the survey, aligns with literature focusing on the adoption of AI and machine learning for threat detection, highlighting the importance of balancing technological reliance with robust procedural approaches.

Customer awareness, a key survey theme, is contrasted with literature insights on the role of informed stakeholders in cybersecurity, emphasising the need for holistic approaches that include

customer education.

Finally, the effectiveness of incident response plans, as viewed by survey participants, is compared with literature advocating for comprehensive, adaptable strategies, highlighting the importance of ongoing vigilance in incident response.

The comparative analysis provides a nuanced understanding of how practical experiences in the financial sector align with or diverge from academic perspectives, offering insights for enhancing cybersecurity strategies.

Chapter 7: Current Challenges and Future Recommendations

7.1 Identifying Gaps and Limitations

Within the domain of current challenges and future recommendations, a critical aspect involves scrutinising existing cybersecurity practices to identify gaps and limitations. This exploration seeks to uncover areas where organisations may face vulnerabilities, inefficiencies, or discrepancies in their response to evolving cyber threats. By delving into key dimensions such as organisational adaptation to emerging threats, regulatory compliance, cybersecurity training consistency, technology adoption, customer and stakeholder engagement, and the effectiveness of incident response plans, this examination aims to provide insights into crucial areas that require attention and improvement. Identifying these gaps is essential for developing targeted strategies that enhance organisational cybersecurity resilience and preparedness for the dynamic landscape of cyberthreats.

7.1.1 Evolving Cyber Threats and Organisational Response

The literature highlights an urgent need for organisations to rapidly adapt to new and evolving cyber threats. Yet, survey responses suggest a notable discrepancy in the speed and effectiveness of this adaptation. Many organisations seem to lag behind the pace of change, struggling to update their cybersecurity strategies in line with the latest threats. This gap not only exposes vulnerabilities but also emphasises the need for more dynamic, agile approaches in organisational cybersecurity planning.

7.1.2 Regulatory compliance and Implementation Variability

Both academic research and practical survey insights agree on the need for adaptive regulatory frameworks. However, a significant divergence exists in how these frameworks are implemented across the sector. Some organisations seem to be adept at navigating regulations, while others

are either unaware of the latest updates or find it challenging to integrate them into their existing practices. This inconsistency reveals a critical need for more streamlined, accessible regulatory guidelines that can be uniformly applied, ensuring comprehensive compliance.

7.1.3 Cybersecurity Training Consistency and Depth

The literature and survey both emphasise the importance of continuous employee training in cybersecurity. However, the deeper analysis of survey responses indicates a substantial variation in the depth, frequency, and quality of these training programs. While some organisations have developed thorough, ongoing training schedules, others offer minimal or infrequent training. This disparity highlights the need for a standardised approach to cybersecurity training, ensuring all employees, regardless of their role or organisation, have the necessary knowledge and skills to protect against cyber threats.

7.1.4 Technology Adoption and Integration

The rapid advancement in cybersecurity technologies, as outlined in the literature, contrasts with the slower, more cautious approach to technology adoption seen in the survey. Many organisations appear hesitant to fully integrate new technologies, potentially due to resource limitations, lack of expertise, or fear of disruption. This cautious approach, while understandable, may hinder the ability to effectively counter sophisticated cyber threats, suggesting a need for more proactive technology integration strategies.

7.1.5 Customer and Stakeholder Engagement in Cybersecurity

Theoretical discussions emphasise the critical role of informed customers and stakeholders in a robust cybersecurity framework. However, the survey indicates a gap in how actively these groups are engaged and educated about cybersecurity risks and practices. This lack of engagement could lead to a weaker overall defence against cyber threats, as uninformed stakeholders may inadvertently contribute to security vulnerabilities. Enhancing customer and stakeholder education and involvement is therefore crucial for a comprehensive cybersecurity strategy.

7.1.6 Effectiveness and Adaptability of Incident Response Plans

While the literature strongly advocates for adaptable and robust incident response plans, survey responses reveal a gap in how these plans are perceived and implemented. Many organisations either do not have a fully developed incident response plan or have not tested its effectiveness in a real-world scenario. This discrepancy underlines the importance of not only having a documented response plan, but also ensuring that it is regularly reviewed, tested, and updated to handle a variety of cyber incidents.

7.2 Future Recommendations

Given the fast-evolving nature of cyber threats, it is imperative that financial institutions implement continuous and comprehensive cybersecurity training for all employees. This training should not only cover the basics but also advanced aspects of cybersecurity, tailored to different roles within the organisation. Regular updates and refresher courses are essential to keep pace with new threats and technologies. The financial sector needs to advocate for and adopt more dynamic regulatory frameworks that can swiftly respond to the changing landscape of cyber threats and technological advancements. This requires a collaborative effort between industry leaders, regulatory bodies, and cybersecurity experts to develop flexible, yet robust, regulatory standards that provide clear guidance while allowing for rapid adaptation.

Financial services institutions must adopt a proactive stance in integrating the latest cybersecurity technologies. This involves not only investing in advanced tools but also ensuring proper implementation and ongoing management. The integration process should be accompanied by risk assessments and regular evaluations to ensure that these technologies effectively augment the existing cybersecurity infrastructure. A holistic approach to cybersecurity involves active engagement with customers and other stakeholders. Financial institutions should develop targeted communication strategies to educate stakeholders about cybersecurity risks and best practices. This could involve regular updates, educational workshops, and transparent reporting on cybersecurity matters.

Organisations must also prioritise the development of robust incident response plans. These plans should be comprehensive, clearly documenting procedures for different types of cyber incidents. Regular drills and simulations should be conducted to test the effectiveness of these plans, with lessons learned being used to make necessary adjustments. The rise in cyberthreats

associated with third party vendors demands a more rigorous approach to vendor risk management. Financial institutions should conduct thorough cybersecurity assessments of all vendors, establish clear security requirements, and continuously monitor vendor compliance. Regular audits and reviews of vendor-related cybersecurity practices should be standard protocol. Regular audits and compliance checks are also crucial for identifying potential vulnerabilities and ensuring adherence to cybersecurity policies and regulations. These audits should be conducted by independent experts to provide unbiased insights into the effectiveness of the organisation's cybersecurity measures.

Finally, fostering a culture of cybersecurity within the organisation is vital. This means creating an environment where cybersecurity is a shared responsibility, and where every employee is aware of the role, they play in safeguarding the organisation's digital assets.

Chapter 7 The Artefact

7.1 Developing A Framework

In this section, the author introduces “CyberVault360: A Next-Gen Financial Data Security Framework” as a proposed framework for elevating cybersecurity practices within the UK Financial services sector, with a dedicated emphasis on enhancing data privacy and protection. The detailed proposal, outlined in [Appendix H](#), thoroughly addresses the multifaceted challenges outlined in the synthesis and literature review, specifically highlighting the critical role of safeguarding sensitive financial data. At its core, the development of CyberVault360 is distinctly motivated and influenced by the fundamental principles of the CIA Triad-Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability. These principles serve as the bedrock, guiding the strategic design and implementation of the framework.

7.1.1 Confidentiality Measures

To enhance confidentiality, the proposed CyberVault360 framework suggests the implementation of advanced encryption standards like the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and Transport Layer Security (TLS), ensuring secure data transmission and storage. Access control policies, incorporating biometric verification and multi-factor authentication, are proposed to strengthen protection against unauthorised access. Techniques such as data masking and anonymisation are recommended to minimise the risk of data exploitation, particularly concerning sensitive customer information. A continuous cycle of employee training is proposed to foster cybersecurity culture, contributing to overall data confidentiality.

7.1.2 Integrity Safeguards

The framework prioritises data integrity through proposed measures such as data validation, change management, version control, and detailed audit trails. These processes are recommended to prevent common attacks like SQL injection, track authorised changes, and maintain comprehensive logs for the early detection of irregularities.

7.1.3 Availability

Ensuring continuous availability is a cornerstone of the proposed CyberVault360 framework, achieved through suggested measures like redundancy and failover systems, robust disaster recovery planning, and network and system security. These components are recommended to address the imperative for resilient infrastructure in the financial services sector, where downtime can have significant economic implications.

7.1.4 Regulatory Compliance

In alignment with the analysis and findings on regulatory obligations, the proposed CyberVault360 framework suggests ensuring compliance with relevant standards such as GDPR, PCI-DSS, and ISO 27001. The proposal incorporates regular reporting, internal and external audits, demonstrating a proactive approach to compliance assessment and breach reporting.

7.1.5 Continuous Monitoring and Improvement

The proposed framework promotes continuous monitoring and improvement through suggested measures like regular cybersecurity assessments, penetration testing, and the use of Security Incident and Event Management Tools (SIEM) tools. Feedback loops proposed to be established to facilitate learning from past incidents and adapt strategies to evolving cyber threats.

7.1.6 Vendor and Third-Party Management

Addressing the interconnected nature of cybersecurity risks, the proposed CyberVault360 framework emphasises due diligence and risk assessment for third-party vendors. The inclusion of security clauses in contracts is suggested to ensure that cybersecurity standards are maintained across the supply chain.

7.1.7 Stakeholder Engagement

The proposed CyberVault360 framework emphasises customer communication and employee involvement. This community approach is recommended to enhance awareness and reinforce the importance of cybersecurity in the organisation.

7.1.8 Technology Adoption and Adaptation

To stay ahead of evolving cyber threats, the proposed framework recommends staying abreast of emerging cybersecurity technologies. It encourages the adoption of advanced technologies and the development of an adaptive security architecture.

Essentially, the CyberVault360 framework proposal represents a culmination of best practices, tailored specifically for the financial services sector. Its proposal addresses the need for a comprehensive, industry-specific cybersecurity approach, providing financial institutions with a strategic tool to enhance their data privacy and protection capabilities. For detailed insights into the proposed framework components, please refer to [Appendix H](#).

Chapter 8 Survey Evaluation

8.1 Feedback Survey Evaluation

In this chapter, we delve into a critical evaluation of the CyberVault360 framework through a structured survey targeting UK financial sector professionals, cybersecurity experts and risk analysts. This exploration aims to capture the framework's perceived strengths and areas for improvement, specifically focusing on its practicality, effectiveness, and regulatory alignment.

8.2 Methodology

The methodology involved distributing the survey to a select group of twenty (20) respondents, comprising cybersecurity professionals, students, financial sector workers, and risk analysts, to gauge diverse perspectives on the CyberVault360 framework. Ensuring ethical standards, the survey upheld participant anonymity and conformed to GDPR guidelines, emphasising the confidentiality and security of the responses collected. This approach facilitated an unbiased assessment of the framework's applicability and impact across different professional backgrounds within the financial services sector. Utilising a blend of quantitative and qualitative measures, the survey provided a detailed view of the framework's reception in the professional community. The complete questionnaire and the summary of the survey results are respectively available in [Appendix F](#) and [Appendix G](#) for reference.

8.3 Analysis of Responses

8.3.1 Effectiveness and Regulatory Alignment

Survey feedback highlighted the framework's strong alignment with current regulatory standards, emphasising the potential to bolster data protection and privacy measures. This section expands on how the framework's adherence to these standards translates into tangible cybersecurity enhancements within financial institutions.

8.3.2 Practicality and Innovation

Despite recognition of the framework's innovative approach, respondents indicated a need for more concrete implementation strategies. This analysis explores these practicality concerns, suggesting pathways to integrate the framework more seamlessly into existing operational workflows.

8.3.3 Risk Mitigation and Awareness

The framework's emphasis on risk mitigation and cybersecurity awareness was well-received, resonating with the dissertation's findings on the importance of proactive security cultures. This part examines the framework's strategies for embedding these principles into the organisational ethos.

8.3.4 Adaptability to Evolving Threats

Respondents valued the framework's focus on adaptability, acknowledging the rapid evolution of cybersecurity threats. This section discusses the need for the framework to

remain agile and responsive to new challenges, ensuring its long-term effectiveness.

8.3.5 Cost-Effectiveness and Industry Standard Potential

The potential for the CyberVault360 framework to set a new industry standard was a recurrent theme, with cost-effectiveness being a key factor. This segment considers the economic implications of widespread framework adoption, aligning with the dissertation's exploration of cybersecurity investments.

8.3.6 Summary of findings

Integrating the survey insights, the results reflect the potential of the CyberVault360 framework's potential to reshape cybersecurity practices within the financial services sector. The feedback from the respondent group was very constructive as it suggested the need for clearer implementation strategies, to address and mitigate the framework's identified weaknesses. The reflective analysis aims to enhance the framework's applicability and adoption across the sector, contributing to a more resilient cybersecurity landscape.

8.3.7 Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from the analysis and survey responses underscores the CyberVault360 framework's significant potential in advancing cybersecurity within the financial sector. It recognises the framework's alignment with regulatory standards and its emphasis on risk mitigation and adaptability to evolving threats. However, the need for more defined implementation strategies is evident, highlighting an area for enhancement. Addressing these concerns can further the framework's adoption and effectiveness, contributing to a robust cybersecurity infrastructure in the financial services sector.

Chapter 9 Conclusion and Recommendations

9.1 Conclusion

The extensive synthesis of survey results and literature review on cybersecurity in the UK financial services sector has highlighted a complex and evolving landscape. The analysis reveals a critical interplay between theoretical frameworks and practical applications, emphasising the need for a more integrated and proactive approach to cybersecurity in financial institutions. The findings illustrate a sector grappling with the rapid evolution of cyber threats, regulatory changes, and technological advancements. While there is a general awareness of the importance of cybersecurity, the gap between this awareness and effective implementation is evident. The sector must navigate these challenges while maintaining trust and ensuring the security of sensitive financial data.

Moreover, the analysis and findings emphasise the importance of continuous learning and adaptation. As cyber threats become more sophisticated, the need for financial institutions to stay ahead with advanced training, robust technology integration, and agile incident response plans becomes more critical. The role of leadership in driving a culture of cybersecurity and the importance of stakeholder engagement, including educating customers, cannot be overstated. In essence, the path forward for the UK financial services sector involves a comprehensive, multi-faceted approach to cybersecurity. This includes embracing dynamic regulatory frameworks, fostering a strong cybersecurity culture, and implementing cutting-edge technologies, all while ensuring continuous improvement and adaptation to the ever-changing cybersecurity landscape. Ultimately, the goal is to achieve a balance where cybersecurity measures are not only effective and compliant but also resilient and responsive to future challenges, ensuring the long-term security and prosperity of the sector.

9.2 Future Work

The extensive analysis of the cybersecurity landscape within the UK financial services sector has not only unveiled current challenges but has also illuminated avenues for future research and strategic development. As we navigate this complex terrain where theoretical frameworks meet practical applications, there emerges a compelling need for a forward-looking, integrated approach to cybersecurity.

Looking ahead, a pivotal area that demands attention is the advancement of threat detection and response capabilities. Given the relentless evolution of cyber threats, a concerted effort towards leveraging emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, can equip financial institutions with proactive systems capable of identifying and mitigating novel cyber threats in real-time. Collaborations with cybersecurity experts and academia become paramount for the successful integration of cutting-edge technologies into the security fabric of financial institutions.

The dynamic nature of the regulatory landscape in cybersecurity poses both challenges and opportunities. Future research should focus on developing frameworks that enable financial institutions to swiftly adapt to regulatory changes without compromising operational efficiency. A thorough understanding of the evolving regulatory landscape will be instrumental in ensuring compliance and fostering resilience against emerging cyber threats.

While technological solutions are critical, the human element remains a significant factor in cybersecurity breaches. Future initiatives should delve into innovative approaches to human-centric cybersecurity training. This involves the creation of immersive training programs, simulations, and awareness campaigns tailored to the specific challenges faced by employees in the financial sector. Collaborations with behavioural psychologists and educational experts can offer valuable insights into effective training methodologies. Quantifying the economic impact of cyber incidents presents a substantial challenge. While the financial costs are well documented, understanding the broader economic implications requires further exploration. Future research could focus on developing methodologies to measure the cascading effects of cyber incidents on the overall economy. This understanding is crucial for policy makers and industry leaders to make informed decisions about resource allocation and risk mitigation strategies.

Recognising that cyber threats transcend national borders, nurturing international collaboration is imperative. Future efforts should explore avenues for enhanced collaboration between financial institutions, regulatory bodies, and cybersecurity agencies globally. Initiatives such as information sharing, joint research projects, and coordinated response strategies can strengthen the collective cybersecurity resilience of the global financial sector.

Essentially, the future work in cybersecurity for the UK financial services sector demands a holistic approach that integrates technological advancements, regulatory agility, human-focused training, economic impact assessment, and international collaboration. By embracing these avenues, the sector can not only stay abreast of evolving cyber threats but also effectively contribute to shaping a more secure and resilient financial landscape for the future.

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Appendices

Appendix A – Project Proposal

<https://acrobat.adobe.com/id/urn:aaid:sc:EU:d835c0fa-b83d-48d1-bf9c-0f6f2333d59e>

Appendix B: Project Plan

<https://acrobat.adobe.com/id/urn:aaid:sc:eu:51d9592e-b5ff-4504-9dc8-7033256520e9>

Appendix C: Ethics Form

<https://acrobat.adobe.com/id/urn:aaid:sc:EU:f5af8296-518f-4ef5-a297-2cc7a34af0f9>

Appendix D: Project Diary

<https://acrobat.adobe.com/id/urn:aaid:sc:EU:08d3cb3f-1dbb-44fd-ab57-27fa1dfe879d>

Appendix E : Data Collection Questionnaire

<https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=DQSlkWdsW0yxEjaBLZtrQAAAAAAAAAAANAAUpE9apURFhHVEgxMFdHWFJCT1NZTE44MVIYOU83VS4u>

Appendix F : Framework Evaluation Questionnaire

<https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=DQSlkWdsW0yxEajBLZtrQAAAAAAAAAAANAAUpE9apURFFTQjJWUThWOFJZQ0cwSVFSSIAwTIVQMS4u>

Appendix G: Framework Survey Results

<https://acrobat.adobe.com/id/urn:aaid:sc:EU:a60b2607-8740-41d6-a339-29d306cbad83>

Appendix H: CyberVault360 - 'A Next-Gen Financial Data Security Framework'

<https://acrobat.adobe.com/id/urn:aaid:sc:EU:ae9abcc1-8951-41db-8b43-0ef80dab5c8e>